

DESIGN, FABRICATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF
GRAPHENE/SILICON SOLAR CELL

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DESIGN, FABRICATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF
GRAPHENE/SILICON SOLAR CELL

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A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the
requirements for the award of the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy

Malaysia-Japan International Institute of Technology
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MARCH 2019

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ABSTRACT

The highest power conversion efficiency (PCE) of single junction silicon (Si) solar cell up to date is 26.3%. The PCE of Si solar cell can be further increased by minimising the optical losses and by the introduction of novel concept Si heterojunction. Optical losses can be minimised by employing Si surface texture and using a transparent electrode. Merging them with the concept of heterojunction, this sparks an idea of graphene/Si solar cell, where graphene serves as a transparent electrode on textured Si (T-Si) surface and it forms metal-semiconductor (MS) junction. Graphene oxide (GO) and reduced graphene oxide (rGO) are low-cost derivatives of graphene that are capable of conformal coating on large area of T-Si. Conformal coating of rGO on T-Si uncovers the possibility of utilising MS junction in building high PCE and low-cost Si heterojunction solar cell. In this work, the photovoltaic performance of rGO/Si by rGO coating on T-Si is investigated. The scopes are; 1) to synthesise GO, 2) to reduce GO into rGO, and 3) to fabricate uniform T-Si and be coated with rGO as a solar cell. GO is synthesised by improved Hummers method as a precursor of rGO. The conversion of GO into rGO is controlled by varying the annealing temperature (AT) from 100–700 °C. The solar cell is fabricated by a coating of rGO thin film on T-Si surface. It was found that the GO film has a non-linear conduction. This is due to the chaotic carrier transportation in GO film, which is described by a variable-range-hopping mechanism with additional contribution from trapped water within the film itself. The effect of trapped water is eliminated after drying of the film. Within a low AT of 100–300 °C on GO film, it produces p-type hybrid rGO-GO. Within high AT of 500–700 °C, the film is an n-type rGO. This occurs due to the dominance of either electron withdrawing or donating groups attached to graphene sp^2 lattice. Non-uniform doping across the film resulted in the non-rectifying junction with n-Si due to Fermi level pinning that allows non-saturation of reverse current. GO film reduced at 400 °C is near charge neutrality and it creates rectifying MS diode upon intimate contact with n-Si. To increase light absorption and increase surface area, Si is textured with inverted micro pyramids by masked anisotropic wet etching. Compared to a flat surface, T-Si significantly reduced reflectance from 53.5% to only 10.4% within the UV-visible range and increased surface area by 43.2%. Excellent wrapping of pyramid sidewalls without suspended GO film is achieved by spin-coating and drop-casting of GO dispersion on T-Si. The rGO/T-Si heterojunction is obtained after annealing at 400 °C. Fabricated rGO/T-Si solar cell with the wrapping of rGO at pyramid sidewalls gives an overall improvement on short circuit current and open circuit voltage compared to solar cell fabricated on flat Si surface. However, the highest PCE obtained at 0.0052% is still considered very small compared to a typical graphene/Si solar cell with PCE more than 10%. High losses in photo-generated current by parasitic series resistance in rGO film are the main cause for low PCE. Future improvement can be done by increasing conductivity of rGO film, or by depositing a more conductive transparent film to improve the lateral conductivity. The findings in this thesis have contributed to the realisation of the novel concept of photovoltaic by MS junction and integration of rGO into existing Si solar cell technology.

ABSTRAK

Kecekapan penukaran kuasa (PCE) yang tertinggi bagi sel suria silikon (Si) satu simpang pada masa ini adalah 26.3%. PCE bagi sel suria Si boleh ditingkatkan lagi dengan meminimumkan kehilangan optik dan pengenalan konsep asli heterosimpang Si. Kehilangan optik boleh diminimumkan dengan menggunakan tekstur permukaan Si dan menggunakan elektrod lutsinar. Menggabungkan mereka dengan konsep heterosimpang, ianya mencetuskan idea bagi sel suria grafin/Si, dimana grafin berfungsi sebagai elektrod lutsinar di atas permukaan Si tertekstur (T-Si) dan membentuk simpang logam-semikonduktor (MS). Grafin oksida (GO) dan grafin oksida terturun (rGO) adalah terbitan kos rendah bagi grafin yang berupaya untuk meyalut secara menyeluruh atas permukaan luas T-Si. Salutan meyalut rGO atas T-Si memungkinkan bagi penggunaan simpang MS dalam pembinaan sel suria Si yang PCE tinggi dan kos rendah. Di dalam kajian ini, prestasi fotovoltan bagi heterosimpang rGO/Si oleh salutan rGO atas T-Si disiasat. Skop-skop adalah; 1) sintesis GO, 2) penurunan GO kepada rGO, dan 3) fabrikasi T-Si seragam dan disalut oleh rGO sebagai sel suria. GO disintesis dengan kaedah Hummers yang diperbaiki sebagai pelopor bagi rGO. GO dikawal penukarannya kepada rGO dengan membezakan suhu penyepuhlindungan (AT) dari 100–700 °C. Sel suria difabrikasi dengan menyalut filem nipis rGO atas permukaan T-Si. Hasil kajian mendapati bahawa filem GO mempunyai konduktif yang tidak lurus. Ini disebabkan oleh pengangkutan kacau-bilau pembawa yang diterangkan oleh mekanisma loncatan julat berubah beserta kesan air terbandung. Kesan air terbandung terhapus selepas filem dikeringkan. Semasa AT rendah 100–300 °C pada filem GO, ianya menghasilkan hibrid rGO-GO jenis-p. Semasa AT tinggi 500–700 °C, filem adalah rGO jenis-n. Kejadian ini disebabkan oleh dominasi sama ada kumpulan-kumpulan pengeluar atau penyumbang elektron pada kekisi sp^2 grafin. Dop yang tak sekata merentasi filem menyebabkan simpang bukan penerus dengan n-Si, dimana pin aras Fermi membenarkan pengaliran arus songsang yang tidak tepu. Filem GO terturun pada 400 °C adalah hampir neutral cas dan ia menghasilkan diod MS penerus jika bersentuhan dengan n-Si. Untuk meningkatkan penyerapan cahaya dan menambah luas permukaan, Si ditekstur dengan piramid songsang mikro oleh punaran anisotropik bertopeng. Berbanding dengan permukaan Si rata, T-Si mengurangkan pantulan secara ketara dari 53.5% ke 10.4% dalam julat UV-nampak dan meningkatkan keluasan permukaan pada 43.2%. Pembalutan sisi piramid yang terbaik tanpa filem GO tergantung diperoleh dengan salutan pusingan dan jatuhan sebaran GO ke atas T-Si. Heterosimpang rGO/T-Si diperoleh selepas penyepuhlindungan pada 400 °C. Sel suria rGO/T-Si dengan salutan rGO memberikan peningkatan pada arus litar pintas dan voltan litar terbuka. Meskipun, PCE yang paling tinggi pada 0.0052% masih lagi dikira jauh lebih rendah jika dibandingkan dengan sel suria grafin/Si yang tipikal dengan PCE lebih dari 10%. Kehilangan besar arus foto-janaan oleh rintangan parasit dalam filem rGO adalah suspek utama bagi PCE yang rendah. Penambahbaikan masa hadapan boleh dilakukan dengan meningkatkan konduktiviti filem rGO, atau dengan meletakkan filem lutsinar yang lebih konduktif untuk memperbaiki konduktiviti sisian. Penemuan dalam tesis ini telah menyumbang kepada realisasi konsep asli fotovoltan oleh simpang MS dan integrasi rGO ke dalam teknologi sel suria Si yang sedia ada.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

2D	-	Two-dimensional
3D	-	Three-dimensional
a-C	-	Amorphous carbon
a-Si	-	Amorphous silicon
Al	-	Aluminium
Al ₂ O ₃	-	Aluminium oxide
AM	-	Air mass
AT	-	Annealing temperature
Au	-	Gold
SBH	-	Schottky barrier height
C	-	Carbon
CVD	-	Chemical vapour deposition
CNTs	-	Carbon nanotubes
DI	-	De-ionised
DOS	-	Density of states
EDG	-	Electron donating groups
EQE	-	External quantum efficiency
EWG	-	Electron withdrawing groups
F-Si	-	Flat silicon
FDTD	-	Finite-difference time-domain
FESEM	-	Field-emission scanning electron microscopy
FF	-	Fill factor
FWHM	-	Full width at half maximum
GO	-	Graphene oxide
h-BN	-	Hexagonal boron nitride
HfO ₂	-	Hafnium dioxide
HJ	-	Heterojunction
HT	-	Heat treatment
I-V	-	Current-voltage
IBC	-	Interdigitated back contact

In	-	Indium
IoT	-	Internet of Things
IPA	-	Isopropyl alcohol
ITO	-	Indium tin oxide
J-V	-	Current density-voltage
MIS	-	Metal-insulator-semiconductor
MLG	-	Multi-layer graphene
MoO _x	-	Molybdenum oxide
MoS ₂	-	Molybdenum disulfide
MS	-	Metal-semiconductor
N ₂	-	Nitrogen gas
NIR	-	Near-infrared
PCE	-	Power conversion efficiency
PERL	-	Passivated emitter, rear locally diffused
PET	-	Polyethylene terephthalate
rGO	-	Reduced graphene oxide
SE	-	Standard error
SEM	-	Scanning electron microscopy
Si	-	Silicon
SiO ₂	-	Silicon dioxide
SiN _x	-	Silicon nitride
Sn	-	Tin
S-Q	-	Shockley-Queisser
STC	-	Standard test condition
T-Si	-	Textured silicon
TE	-	Thermionic emission
TEF	-	Transverse electric field
TMAH	-	Tetramethyl-ammonium-hydroxide
TMF	-	Transverse magnetic field
UV	-	Ultraviolet
VRH	-	Variable-range-hopping

LIST OF SYMBOLS

α	-	Absorption coefficient
A	-	Absorption constant
A^*	-	Richardson constant
A_j	-	Junction area
B	-	Magnetic field
X	-	Electron affinity
D	-	Depth of silicon pyramid
ϵ_0	-	Permittivity of free space
ϵ_S	-	Semiconductor dielectric constant
e	-	Elementary charge
E_0	-	Free-electron energy level
E_c	-	Conduction band
E_F	-	Fermi level
E_g	-	Band gap
E_v	-	Valence band
E_{\max}	-	Maximum electric field
Φ	-	Work function
Φ_B	-	Schottky barrier height
Φ_i	-	Effective barrier height
f	-	Numerical factor in van der Pauw
η	-	Diode ideality factor
h	-	Planck constant
\hbar	-	Reduced Planck constant
I_0	-	Reverse saturation current
I_{ph}	-	Photo-generated current
I_{sc}	-	Short circuit current
I_D	-	Raman D band
I_G	-	Raman G band
J_0	-	Reverse saturation current density
J_{ph}	-	Photo-generated current density

J_{sc}	-	Short circuit current density
k	-	Boltzmann constant
λ	-	Light wavelength
μ	-	Carrier mobility
m_n^*	-	Density of states mass of electron
m_p^*	-	Density of states mass of hole
ν	-	Light frequency
n	-	Carrier concentration
n_0	-	Thermal-equilibrium electron concentration
n_i	-	Intrinsic concentration
N_a	-	Acceptor concentration
N_c	-	Effective density of states in the conduction band
N_d	-	Donor concentration
N_v	-	Effective density of states in the valence band
p_0	-	Thermal-equilibrium hole concentration
P_{in}	-	Incident light power
R_s	-	Series resistance
R_{sh}	-	Shunt resistance
R_{sq}	-	Sheet resistance
σ_{dc}	-	Direct current conductivity
σ_{op}	-	Optical conductivity
S	-	Spacing between silicon pyramids
S_{eff}	-	Effective surface recombination velocity
S_{front}	-	Front surface recombination velocity
S_{rear}	-	Front surface recombination velocity
τ_{eff}	-	Effective minority carrier lifetime
τ_{bulk}	-	Minority carrier lifetime in bulk
t	-	Thickness
T	-	Temperature
T_{op}	-	Optical transmittance
V_{oc}	-	Open circuit voltage
W	-	Width of silicon pyramid
W_d	-	Depletion width

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Solar energy harvesting device by silicon (Si) solar cell is a mature technology and it comprises up to 95% of all the solar cells produced in 2017 with an estimated worldwide market of 94.6 GW [1]. Si solar cell is a solid-state semiconductor device which harnesses the everlasting energy supply by the sun in the form of light into electricity. Si is one of the abundant elements found in the Earth's crust. Material usage for Si solar cell in current technology is only around 4 g/W_p [1]. In conventional Si solar cell, the photovoltaic capability is provided by the formed metallurgical junction of p-type and n-type Si. It involves diffusion of the n-type dopant into p-type Si substrate.

Figure 1.1(a) shows the energy band diagram of n⁺,p,p⁺ junctions in conventional Si solar cell under equilibrium [2]. Bands bending in the vicinity of diffused regions indicate the gradient in carrier concentration, n for both electron and hole. There are two forces that exist across the junctions, which are chemical and electrical potentials. Under the equilibrium, they are identical in magnitude but in they function in opposite direction, so that no net force acting on the carrier and Fermi energy, E_F is kept constant. Figure 1.1(b) shows the condition of maximum power point under illumination where excess carriers are generated within the material [2]. Excess carriers split initial E_F into two quasi- E_F and they drive electrons toward the n⁺ region while holes toward the p⁺ region. A successful collection of photo-excited electrons and holes before recombination provides a magnitude of current flow in the complete electrical circuit.

The limit of light-electric power conversion efficiency (PCE) is defined by the bandgap, E_g of the material [3]. According to the Shockley-Queisser limit (S-Q)

theory, also known as detailed balance limit as shown in Figure 1.1(c), Si with E_g of 1.12 eV is limited to maximum PCE of 33.3%. In a fabricated device, the practical limit of PCE is found around 75% of theoretical S-Q limit. Current PCE record of 26.3% from single-crystal Si solar cell is slightly above 75% of S-Q limit [4]. The typical PCE of commercial single-crystal Si p-n junction solar cells are in the range of 16–18%, while multi-crystal Si p-n junction solar cells are slightly lower in the range of 15–17% [5]. The deviation of measured PCE from the fabricated device in respect to the S-Q limit is mainly due to the recombination losses. For example in a conventional Si n^+,p,p^+ junctions solar cell, rear metal/semiconductor interface p^+ region contributes 49% in percentage, p-type absorber region contributes 26%, while the front n^+ phosphorus contributes 24% in the overall recombination losses [2].

Figure 1.1 Energy band diagrams of a conventional n^+,p,p^+ Si solar cell in: (a) Equilibrium; (b) Maximum power point under illumination [2]; and (c) Shockley-Queisser efficiency limit as a function of materials band gap [3]

Research and development of Si solar cells are still ongoing and being actively participated all around the world. The aims are straightforward, which are to increase the PCE while at the same time to reduce the involved material and production costs [5]. The PCE of Si solar cell can be increased by minimising carrier recombination, lowering parasitic series resistance, and reducing optical loss. In this project, special attention was given on the effort in reducing optical loss because it is first issue need to be considered, determining how much light energy could be absorbed by Si substrate for generation of photocurrent. In short, optical loss in Si solar cell can be reduced either by texturing the Si surface with micro/ nanostructures, or by replacing the use

of the opaque metal grid, or by depositing anti-reflection coating, or by the combination all of them.

In another perspective, both concern on PCE and cost also could be tackled by an introduction of a novel cell design with heterojunction between Si and other materials [6]. Materials of choice for potential heterojunction with matured Si platform attracted a profound research interest within the existing Si solar cell research groups and also advanced materials research groups [2]. The introduction of the heterojunction concept between Si and advanced materials potentially leads to the fabrication of multiple junction solar cells, exceeding the PCE limit of 33.3% as defined by the S-Q theory.

The market for Si solar cell is not limited only to large-area energy harvesting activity. In another point of view, the solar cell is a robust solution for de-centralised power supply and self-powering electronic devices. In the near future, it is envisaged that billions of small, portable and intercommunicating sensor devices will be dispatched out to the market. This is more likely a convincing projection, but only true if the Internet of Things (IoT) is successfully spread out within and accepted by worldwide communities [7]. Some of these billions of sensor devices may be designed to tap electricity from wall supply, but most of them are intended to be scattered and wireless so that perpetual operation powered by the solar cell will be the next huge market. In preparing for an optimistic situation where the market of self-sustaining IoT sensor node will be blooming in the near future, researchers need to start working with efficient, cheap, miniaturised, and on-chip solar cell. The selection and evaluation of material for Si heterojunction solar cell is a big topic due to the large variety of materials and their respective processing technology.

1.2 Research Motivation

In this work, the sole motivation is identifying the potential heterojunction between Si and advanced nanomaterials towards high-efficiency and low-cost Si-based solar cell. Carbon (C) is another abundant element that can be easily found on

earth. Crystalline carbon has diverse structures, textures and properties that are exploitable for a specific device such as a solar cell. Explicit attention set onto carbon nanomaterials, where they exist in various stable allotropes such as amorphous carbon (a-C), fullerene C₆₀, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene, and several others [8]. Among the known carbon allotropes, CNTs and graphene nanomaterials are unique and have shown positive feedback in respect to the feasibility of C/Si heterojunction solar cell. CNTs were physically discovered in 1991 [9].

The first CNTs/Si solar cell was fabricated in 2007 with designated junction area of 0.49 cm² and delivered PCE of 1.31% [10]. Meanwhile, graphene was physically discovered in 2004 [11]. The first graphene/Si solar cell was fabricated in 2010 with designated junction area of 0.1 cm² and delivered PCE of 1.7% [12]. The progress of both CNTs/Si and graphene/Si solar cells is moving forward rapidly from their initial starting points of the year 2007 and 2010, respectively. Both CNTs/Si and graphene/Si solar cells already scored beyond 15% PCE mark after 2015 [8]. At present, the highest reported PCE of CNTs/Si solar cell is 17% for junction area of 0.008 cm² [13]. In the second place, PCE of 15.1% is recorded for CNTs/Si solar cell with a larger junction area of 0.15 cm² [14].

The present record for graphene/Si solar cell is 16.17% for junction area of 0.078 cm² [15]. It is followed by PCE of 15.8% with undisclosed junction area [16], and PCE of 15.6% for junction area of 0.11 cm² [17]. Although the score of CNTs/Si and graphene/Si solar cells are head-to-head, graphene holds a prominent advantage compared to the CNTs in term of optical characteristic. The transparent conducting CNTs film is basically formed by a random percolation of the 1-dimensional CNTs networks in the lateral direction. Meanwhile, graphene is a continuous sheet of 2-dimensional (2D) crystalline carbon with superior light transmittance. In consequence, in CNTs/silicon solar cells even their PCE are remarkably good in more than 10%, their short circuit current density (J_{sc}) however are quite low not even surpassing 30 mA/cm² [18–21].

Figure 1.2 summarises the research timeline on graphene/Si heterojunction solar cell with indicated major events. The starting point was definitely from 2004

after the first physical discovery of graphene by mechanical exfoliation (mechanical cleavage). This gives rise in a demonstration of graphene in various kind of electronic devices including the solar cell. Beyond 2010 until present can be considered as rapid progress for graphene/Si solar cell due to efforts in assimilating the existing feature of Si solar cell, especially on the reduction of optical loss in this new concept of Si heterojunction. In parallel progress, an old topic on the preparation of graphitic oxide dated back in 1958 re-surfaced after the published article described the improved method in 2010 to produce a high yield of good quality graphene oxide (GO). This is important because graphene derivatives of GO and reduced graphene oxide (rGO) are low-cost alternative and they might be attempting if the efficiency of the fabricated solar cell can be demonstrated at a reasonably high value.

Figure 1.2 Research timeline on graphene/Si heterojunction solar cell with highlighted several major events

A single-atom-thick of graphene is highly transparent with a light transmittance of 97.7% [22]. Figure 1.3(a) and (b) show the transparency of single, bi-layer, and up to 5-layer of graphene. A single layer of graphene absorbs $2.3 \pm 0.1\%$ and reflects negligibly $<0.1\%$ of light, independent of light wavelength, λ . Adding each layer of graphene simply adds another 2.3% in light absorption. Increasing the number of layers improves the electrical conductivity, σ of graphene due to the increase in density of states (DOS) [23]. Since one of the functions of graphene in a solar cell is

to serve as a transparent conductor, so there is basically a trade-off between its σ and light transmittance as a function of film thickness.

Besides serving a function as a transparent electrode, graphene is a 2D metal that forms a rectifying metal-semiconductor (MS) junction with Si [12]. This is the main motivation in this work. The details on the formation of MS junction are included in Appendix A. For the isolated carbon atom, electrons fill orbitals of $1s^2 2s^2 2p^2$. For the graphene crystal where an atom is bonded covalently (σ - σ bonds) to three neighbouring atoms, orbitals $2s$ and $2p$ hybridise into sp^3 with a free electron from p -orbital to form the conjugated π and π^* band [24]. The covalent σ - σ bond is very rigid and provides mechanical strength for graphene, while the de-localised π electron is responsible for electrical conductivity. The conduction band, E_c and valence band, E_v of graphene touch each other at six points in the reciprocal space at K and K' corners of hexagonal Brillouin zone [24]. Thus, graphene can be classified either as a 2D metal, semi-metal, or zero E_g semiconductor.

Figure 1.3 (a) Photograph of single and bi-layer graphene under 50 μm aperture indicating their light transmittance; and (b) Transmittance of graphene within visible light according to theory and measurement. The inset shows transmittance dependency with a number of layer [22]

The energy dispersion at the K point is linear as obtained from the Hamiltonian tight-binding approximation. In intrinsic condition, work function, Φ of graphene is located at Dirac point. Electrons in low DOS behave like a massless particle with Fermi velocity, which is $\sim 1/300$ of the speed of light in vacuum [23]. Giant carrier

mobility, μ could be measured during ballistic carrier transport, but with a universal minimum σ of $4e^2/\pi h$. Conductive, high transmittance, and capability to form rectifying MS junction with Si, are the characteristics that the researchers are looking for to build a novel structure of high-efficiency and low-cost Si-based solar cell. No serious concerns are given on giant μ and ballistic transport for solar cell application.

1.3 Problem Statement

The origin of the problem was started with the efforts to improve the efficiency of Si solar cell by a reduction in optical loss and by the introduction of novel concept Si heterojunction with graphene. As mentioned, the approaches to reduce the optical loss in Si solar cell are well known, especially by Si surface texture and by replacing the opaque metal contact with graphene transparent electrode. The problem now is how to deal with the concept of graphene/Si heterojunction by using textured Si surface. It is related with the production of graphene and the coating of graphene on the textured Si surface to address both issues in reducing the optical loss and demonstration of the novel concept of MS junction graphene on textured Si surface.

The first subject is about the method of obtaining suitable large area, low-cost, yet with the acceptable quality of graphene. Figure 1.4(a) to (i) show several methods in obtaining graphene that has been reported. The methods of obtaining graphene are reviewed in ref. [25]; they are mechanical cleavage of graphite by scotch tape, anodic bonding cleavage by electrostatic interaction, photo-exfoliation by laser ablation, aqueous phase exfoliation, epitaxial growth on SiC, growth on carbon-containing metal by precipitation, chemical vapour deposition (CVD), molecular beam epitaxy, and chemical synthesis by assembling polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons through surface-mediated reactions. The most common methods in obtaining graphene for an investigation at device-level application are narrowed down to mechanical cleavage, growth on SiC, CVD, and aqueous phase exfoliation [23]. Table 1.1 compares and evaluates the suitability of graphene obtained those three methods in the prospect of graphene/Si solar cell.

Figure 1.4 Production of graphene: (a) Mechanical cleavage; (b) Anodic bonding; (c) Photo-exfoliation; (d) Aqueous phase exfoliation; (e) Growth on SiC; (f) Precipitation from carbon-containing metal; (g) Chemical vapour deposition; (h) Molecular beam epitaxy; (i) Chemical synthesis from benzene [25]

Mechanical cleavage exfoliates 3-dimensional (3D) graphite into pristine single-layer and single-crystal graphene. High-quality graphene by this method demonstrates high carrier mobility around $10000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ even at room temperature [11]. However, the size of exfoliated graphene is small typically below $100 \mu\text{m}$ and not possible to be utilised for large area device. Epitaxial growth on SiC is capable of producing single-crystal graphene. This can be done by annealing the surfaces of SiC either Si (0001) or C (0001)-terminated at a high temperature more than $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under ultra-high vacuum. It evaporates the Si and induces the graphitisation [26,27]. However, it involves a large cost for the process and the cost of the SiC substrate itself makes it not an option for the desired graphene/Si solar cell application.

Table 1.1 Comparison between mechanical exfoliation, chemical vapour deposition and aqueous phase exfoliation in terms of suitability for solar cell

Method	Product	Suitability for solar cell application	Ref.
Mechanical cleavage	Single-crystal graphene	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not possible due to very low yield. • The lateral size of graphene is small in the scale of a micrometre. 	[11]
Epitaxial growth on SiC	Cracked single-crystal graphene	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible but not desirable due to the high cost of SiC substrate and high-temperature process >1000 °C. • Large area film is achievable but with a crack due to lattice mismatch between graphene and SiC. 	[26,27]
Chemical vapour deposition	Multi-crystal graphene	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible growth of a large area of graphene as a continuous film. • However, the growth process is costly with the temperature around 1000 °C. • Suitable if the transfer of graphene onto Si can be done with minimum interface defect. • Not suitable to be transferred onto a textured Si surface. 	[28,29]
Aqueous phase exfoliation	Graphene oxide sheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible to produce a large area of the graphene oxide film. • Appealing because due to the low-cost for given high volume production. • Suitable to be deposited both on polished and textured Si surface. • However, the conductivity of the film needs to be increased to be practical in device-level application. • Functionalised graphene offers other characteristics such as higher light transmittance and more hydrophilicity. 	[33,34]

Large area graphene is made possible to be grown on catalytic metal such as copper and nickel by CVD [28]. The process requires a high-temperature chamber at 1000 °C to grow graphene on carbon-soluble metal from carbon-containing gas such as methane. According to pioneering work on CVD graphene, the process could provide centimetre-scaled multi-crystal graphene film with mobility as high as 4050 cm²/Vs [29]. Considering the fact that large area and high-quality graphene could be obtained by this method, capital investment on equipment and high-temperature process are justified. Thus, CVD graphene is almost cost-effective and it is widely used for the demonstration of various types of devices including investigation on graphene/Si solar cells in previous works [30]. To fabricate graphene/Si solar cell, graphene growth on catalytic metal needs to be wet transferred onto the Si surface because graphene cannot be directly growth on Si substrate [12].

The second subject is about the coverage of graphene film on the Si surface. The process of wet transfer of graphene on Si is challenging to avoid crack, break and wrinkle of multi-crystal graphene film for ideal formation of MS junction. Even the target Si surface is just flat after chemical-mechanical polishing; CVD graphene could not perfectly cover the entire Si area due to physical imperfection during growth and wet transfer. Figure 1.5(a) and (b) illustrate the imperfect coverage of graphene on Si and one of the previous research work suggested the use of gold (Au) nanoparticles to fill the crack [31]. However, that method is more like an effort to minimise the after-effect and does not address the root problem. The situation is more critical for the case of textured Si surface. For solar cell application, Si needs to be maximised in term of the light absorption and the most reliable way to achieve this is by introducing micro-scale texture on the front surface [32]. Imperfect coverage of CVD graphene on textured Si surface is the main concern in this work; it contributes to inferior characteristics of MS junction and they are reviewed in the next chapter.

The GO by aqueous phase exfoliation is identified as the answer in obtaining conformal wrapping of graphene on textured Si surface. In this route, 3D graphite is first oxidised into graphite oxide either by chlorate or permanganate as illustrated in Figure 1.6(a). Graphite oxide then being exfoliated into the mass volume of GO effortlessly by stirring [33,34]. Figure 1.6(b) illustrates the GO sheet with various

oxygen functional groups such as hydroxyl, epoxide, carbonyl, and carboxylic attached to its basal plane and edges [25]. Oxidised graphene is now significantly with lower electrical conductivity compared to graphene which obtained by mechanical cleavage, epitaxial growth on SiC and CVD. De-oxygenation of GO into rGO as shown in Figure 1.6(c) results in defective graphene but significantly restores its conductivity to be practical for device-level application [35].

Figure. 1.5 (a) Cracked CVD graphene results in incomplete coverage of graphene on Si substrate. (b) The proposed solution of filling the crack by Au nanoparticles [31]

Figure 1.6 (a) Oxidation of bulk graphite either by chlorate or permanganate routes [36]; (b) Model of graphene oxide with various types of oxygen functional group attaching to aromatic regions; and (c) Model of reduced graphene oxide with defected lattice after de-oxygenation [25]

The exfoliation of 3D graphite oxide produces micrometre-sized GO sheets in similar analogy to mechanical cleavage. Mass volume of GO sheets are dispersed in water or organic solvent before forming a continuous film on a target substrate by several coating techniques such as electrophoretic deposition, spin or spray coating, dip coating, transfer printing, and Langmuir-Blodgett method [35]. Coating of GO sheets are different compared to wet transfer of CVD graphene, where coating on the non-planar surface is highly possible since individual GO sheet is small. After the conformal coating is achieved, GO film then can be reduced into rGO to complete the device. Conformal wrapping of rGO onto textured Si surface is expected to form ideal MS junction for solar energy harvesting. In an optimistic point of view, it will lead the researchers towards a novel concept of highly efficient and low-cost Si heterojunction solar cell, either for large or small area solar energy harvesting.

1.4 Objective and Scopes

The objective of this work is to obtain a large area coverage of rGO film on the uniformly textured Si surface and investigate the photovoltaic performance of rGO/Si heterojunction solar cell. There are three scopes and they are described as follows

- (a) To synthesise GO dispersion by aqueous phase exfoliation, form a continuous film of GO, and study the electrical characteristic of wet GO film and dried GO film.
- (b) To reduce GO film into rGO film by thermal annealing for restoring its electrical conductivity and study the diode properties of GO/n-Si and rGO/n-Si heterojunctions.
- (c) To design and fabricate uniform Si surface texture and study the photovoltaic performance of rGO/n-Si heterojunction solar cell.

1.5 Thesis Organisation

This thesis contains 7 chapters. Chapter 1 provides the introduction for the topic, describes the motivation, specifically points out the current problem to be investigated, states the objective and defining the scopes. In Chapter 2, previous research works on the integration of graphene, GO and rGO into Si solar cell are reviewed. Discussions in Chapter 2 are the extension for the introduced contents in Chapter 1 and focuses on the declared problem statement. In Chapter 3, research flowcharts are presented for each scope. The chapter elaborates in detail on the experimental methods for device fabrication and characterisation. Related formulations used to extract parameter from measurement are explained in particular.

Chapters 4, 5 and 6 discuss experimental results for the defined scopes. Chapter 4 is the discussion for the first scope, which is about the synthesis of GO and characterisation of GO film. Chapter 4 explains the effect of trapped water within the GO film on its electrical characteristic before proceeded to be used in the solar cell. Chapter 5 is the discussion for the second scope, which is about transition diode properties during thermal reduction of GO on n-Si. Chapter 5 explains the effect of annealing temperature on GO film and after forming a junction with n-Si. Chapter 6 is the discussion for the third scope, which is about rGO on textured Si solar cell. Chapter 6 elaborates the output of optical simulation on Si microstructure and measured light reflectance from the textured surface. Then, the chapter explains the photovoltaic performance of rGO/n-Si solar cell fabricated using textured Si. Finally, Chapter 7 concludes the findings in this thesis and recommends the direction for future work.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF INTEGRATION OF GRAPHENE, GRAPHENE OXIDE AND REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE IN SILICON SOLAR CELL

2.1 Introduction to the Photovoltaic of Silicon Solar Cell

This chapter starts with a brief overview of the basic of silicon (Si) photovoltaic to refresh and to guide the author in understanding the performance indicators in the solar cell. The generation of direct current by Si p-n junction relies on the photovoltaic activity of the semiconducting material. Under thermal equilibrium, there are depletion region and gradient of carrier concentration within the p-n junction. Upon illumination, photon energy that is equal or larger than the optical bandgap, E_g of the semiconductor will excite an electron from the valence band, E_v into the conduction band, E_c . The gradient in quasi-Fermi energies and distinguished carrier conductivity will induce movement and collection of the photo-generated carriers [30]. The current density, J and open circuit voltage, V_{oc} can be obtained by the relation of

$$J = J_{sc} - J_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{eV}{\eta kT}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (2.1)$$

$$V_{oc} = \frac{\eta kT}{e} \ln \left[\frac{J_{sc}}{J_0} + 1 \right] \quad (2.2)$$

where J_{sc} is the short circuit current density, J_0 is the reverse saturation current density, e is the constant of the elementary charge, η is the diode ideality factor, k is the Boltzmann constant, and T is the temperature [30]. Under the standard test condition 1-sun with incident light power, $P_{in} = 100 \text{ mW/cm}^2$, the fill factor (FF) for the solar cell can be obtained based on

$$FF = \frac{J_{\max} V_{\max}}{J_{sc} V_{oc}} \times 100\% \quad (2.3)$$

which is basically the ratio of maximum current density, J_{\max} and maximum voltage, V_{\max} to the product of J_{sc} and V_{oc} [30]. The power conversion efficiency (PCE) can be defined as

$$PCE = \frac{J_{sc} V_{oc} FF}{P_{in}} \quad (2.4)$$

which is representing the product of J_{sc} , V_{oc} and FF in respect to P_{in} [30]. In a mature technology of Si solar cell, by introducing of novel cell design with the integration of new materials into the device architecture, improvement in every performance indicator as described is possible to maximize the light-electricity conversion.

2.2 Background of High-Efficiency Silicon Solar Cell

The title of the highest efficiency monocrystalline Si solar cell was long held by a group from University of New South Wales at the value of 24% in 1990 using the architecture of passivated emitter, rear locally diffused (PERL) [37]. The record was adjusted to 25% for the PERL cell in 1998 [38]. The record remained until the introduction of large area, Si interdigitated back contact (IBC) and heterojunction (HJ) with 25.6% efficiency by Panasonic team in 2014 [39]. Not long after the breakthrough, using the similar architecture of Si IBC-HJ, in 2017 a team from Kaneka reports currently holds the highest efficiency for the single junction at the value of 26.3% [4]. This value is not far from the estimated PCE limit of 28.8% for the 80 μm -thick Si with Lambertian light trapping [40].

The PERL cell is an improvement made based on classic structure but emphasises on passivation and selective doping under contact as shown in Figure 2.1. Classic structure is long commercialised for both single and multi-crystal Si; it comprises the use of p-type Si as a substrate, shallow n-doped on front surface, front

surface texturisation and deposition of anti-reflection coating to reduce light loss, and finally screen-printing front/rear metal contact followed by firing [5].

Figure 2.1 Components and features of Si solar cell based on classic and IBC design [2]. Features included by those structures may be interchanged

The PERL cell allows a smaller contact area at selectively p⁺-doped (rear) and n⁺-doped (front) region, while the remaining is passivated by silicon dioxide (SiO₂) to minimise the recombination [38]. Using p-type Si substrate, the junction profile of the PERL cell from top to bottom is n⁺,n,p,p⁺. The IBC architecture in Figure 2.1 eliminates front contact on the cell, where both passivated anode and cathode are at the rear side under selectively doped n⁺ and p⁺. This avoids shadowing on the front side by metal fingers and busbars, while at the same time passivation of the textured surface could be done more effectively. The HJ more accurately is not a third architecture after classic and IBC. Instead, it refers to the integration of different materials rather than crystalline Si to create the metallurgical junctions. The common material of choice is hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si), in the form of either intrinsic, p-doped or n-doped. The integration of HJ in classic structure almost requires transparent conducting oxide on the front surface before the metal grid to provide a more efficient lateral conductivity [41].

Table 2.1 compares the performance of high-efficiency Si solar cells based on PERL, IBC and IBC-HJ design. Since HJ is not restricted to the classic design, merging the concept of HJ with IBC architecture a record with higher efficiency than the previous record of 25% possible. Using n-type Si substrate, the junction profile of Kaneka 26.3% Si IBC-HJ solar cell is n⁺,i,n,i,p⁺, which involves no doping by diffusion on Si substrate but the junction is formed by thin film deposition of doped a-Si. In spite of the higher cost of n-type compared to the conventional p-type Si wafer as a substrate, the need for n-type replacing p-type substrate is a trend for high-efficiency Si solar cell [41].

In p-type Si substrate, boron dopant is found forming boron-oxygen complexes under exposure to light, which is very undesirable and contributes to carrier recombination. It is important to emphasise that 25% efficiency PERL cell is demonstrated with an area of 4 cm², while 26.3% IBC-HJ Kaneka cell is 180 cm². This means a lot of things; especially on the manufacturing side where lithography, thin film deposition, diffusion, metallisation, and material handling are already practically considered for mass production and commercialisation.

Table 2.1 Comparison of several high-efficiency single junction Si-based solar cells from four main architectures

Design	Area (cm ²)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Ref.
PERL	4.0	42.2	706	82.8	24.70	[42]
	4.0	41.6	704	83.5	24.50	[43]
IBC	4.0	38.9	727	78.4	22.14	[44]
	9.0	39.9	724	74.5	21.50	[45]
IBC-HJ	180.0	42.3	744	83.8	26.30	[4]
	143.7	41.8	740	82.7	25.60	[39]

In another concern, the classic top/rear structure will hardly exceed the 25% efficiency mark set by PERL without opting for IBC and HJ. Except there is one reported so far by Richter et al. in 2017 with the value of 25.7% [46]. They use n-type Si substrate with thin tunnel oxide as a modification based on classical top/rear structure, with careful consideration in minimising Shockley-Read-Hall recombination in bulk Si. Tunnelling oxide between silicon and metal contact thus can be regarded as metal-insulator-semiconductor (MIS) diode, which gives them a junction profile of MIS-n,p⁺,p⁺⁺. The insulator needs to be very thin, i.e. less than 2 nm to make carrier tunnelling possible in MIS diode and improves V_{oc} in the solar cell [47]. The usage of SiO₂ and aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) tunnelling insulator and molybdenum oxide (MoO₃) hole transport layer has been reviewed by Battaglia et al. in building a high-efficiency Si solar cell [2].

HJ of Si with other materials rather than a-Si are still limited to lab work and they do not score as high as the tabulated data in Table 2.1. One could observe that the effort for HJ is not only limited to active materials (p-n) junction but also extending to the replacement of opaque contact with transparent conducting oxide. If we exclude the IBC design, the use of a front transparent electrode indeed is a promising attribute in cell design because it offers lower parasitic light absorption and reflection by those metals. However, conventional metallisation by screen printing and annealing is very inexpensive compared to a transparent electrode, such as indium tin oxide (ITO). In the last few decades, the non-linear current with rectifying characteristic has been confirmed for the ITO/n-Si junction [48]. Those ITO, if could be replaced with

graphene, would lead us to a robust solution of low-cost HJ. Perhaps, metallurgical doping to form a p-n junction and opaque metallisation would be omitted in the next cell architecture if this integration is proven feasible. Unfortunately, at this stage, it is not the case and the factors of hindrance will be discussed shortly in the next section.

2.3 Present Status of Graphene on Silicon Solar Cell

An extensive literature study pertaining to this project has been published and can be found in ref. [30]. In this section, contents will be delivered based on a summary of an important topic from that article. The fundamental of metal-semiconductor (MS) junction has been elaborated in the previous chapter and it is a prerequisite in order to understand the photovoltaic performance of graphene/Si HJ. The first report on demonstration graphene/Si HJ as a solar cell is by Li et al. in 2010 [12]. The structure of this cell is shown in Figure 2.2(a), being constructed by wet transferring of chemical vapour deposition (CVD) graphene onto the opened window of SiO₂ (exposed n-Si substrate). The metal contact is deposited on the substrate prior to wet transfer. Until recently, experimental works by various researchers who are working on graphene/Si solar cell are still based on this structure. In their work, two cells with a junction area of 0.1 and 0.5 cm² are fabricated, as shown in Figure 2.2(b).

Under illumination, MS junction of graphene/n-Si separates the photo-excited electron-hole pairs (hole diffused into graphene, electron diffused to the ohmic rear electrode), as illustrated in Figure 2.2(c). Semilog J-V for both cells under standard test condition (STC) is shown in Figure 2.2(d), where the smaller area exhibits a better PCE of 1.65%, compared to the larger counterpart with PCE of 1.34%. The causes of mediocre efficiency are due to uncontrollable carrier recombination and poor light absorption. The Schottky barrier height (SBH) is estimated in the range of 0.75–0.80 eV, depletes the carrier in n-Si approximately 0.5–0.7 μm.

Figure 2.2 (a) Structure of the graphene/Si solar cell. (b) Semilog I-V plot of graphene/Si junction with an area of 0.1 and 0.5 cm². (c) Energy band diagram of junction under illumination. (d) J-V characteristic of devices under dark and light [12]

The progress of the graphene/Si solar cell from 2010 is quite accelerated. At present, the highest PCE of 16.17% is achieved by Kim et al. for the junction of graphene with Si quantum dots [15]. Here, the details on their device will not be elaborated (because of least importance in respect to the direction of this thesis). The trend of improvement versus year of the article being published can be referred to Figure 2.3. One could learn that improvement J_{sc} is a major contribution for overall increment in PCE, compared to the improvement in V_{oc} and FF.

Table 2.2 summarises the contribution of different features on improving the PCE of graphene/Si solar cell. The J_{sc} is always related to the capability of Si to absorb the incident light ($h\nu > E_g$). Higher light absorption proportionally increases the photo-generated carrier and output current from the solar cell. Meanwhile, V_{oc} is related to the SBH of graphene/Si HJ.

Figure 2.3 Improvement in reported graphene/Si solar cells in term of J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF, and PCE. The dotted line is a level for first graphene/Si solar cell from ref. [12]. Plots are reproduced from ref. [30]

Higher SBH results in wider depletion region in Si, thus the presence of gradient carrier concentration within the depletion region will induce separation and collection of the photo-generated carrier. The excellence of FF came from the minimisation of series resistance, R_s and maximisation of shunt resistance, R_{sh} . Let us consider the resistances by bulk Si and metallisation are consistent for each fabricated device, then graphene's conductivity plays the role in determining how good the overall R_s in graphene/Si solar cell. For the R_{sh} , high carrier recombination results in low R_{sh} in the cell. R_{sh} can be maximised by good Si surface passivation and insertion of the interlayer to assist carrier collection at the interface of graphene/Si HJ.

This project focuses more on J_{sc} improvement, for the junction build from the conformal coating of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) on textured Si surface. Hence in the next section, literature will be discussed in detail about J_{sc} in graphene/Si solar cell, Si surface texture, and rGO as an alternative for the graphene. Again, readers are suggested to refer to ref. [30] for detailed review and assessment on the remaining merit; especially on V_{oc} , FF, and additional issues on the stability/ reliability of graphene/Si solar cell.

Table 2.2 Enhancement features and their contribution on improving merit of performance in graphene/Si solar cell

Merit	Feature	Contribution
J_{sc}	Si surface texture	Micro/nanostructure improves light absorption
	Anti-reflection coating	Thin insulator coating reduces reflection
V_{oc}	Graphene work function	High work function increases SBH
	Tunnelling insulator	Thin barrier accumulates the minority carrier
FF	Graphene conductivity	High conductivity reduces series resistance
	Si surface passivation	Passivation reduces surface recombination
	Tunnelling insulator	Accumulation reduces interface recombination
	Hole transport layer	Hole transport reduces interface recombination

2.4 Improvement of Photo-Current by Silicon Surface Texture

Reducing optical losses is the key to improve the photocurrent generation within Si absorber. Polished Si surface has a high reflectance of average around 40% in the UV-visible-NIR range and poor absorption, especially in the long wavelength region [49]. Because of poor light absorption, a photon with $\lambda = 1.1 \mu\text{m}$ needs to travel around 1 cm inside Si substrate before it is successfully absorbed. Photon enters the Si substrate from the front surface, travelling down to the rear surface, then reflected back to the front surface. The process continues until successful absorption of a photon. In the ideal case, if it is assumed that no losses of the photo-generated carrier during collection to the external circuitry, the J_{sc} then can be described as

$$J_{sc} = J_{ph} = \frac{e}{hc} \int \lambda P_{in}(\lambda) EQE(\lambda) \cdot d\lambda \quad (2.5)$$

where J_{ph} is the photo-generated current density, P_{in} is the incident light power, and EQE is the external quantum efficiency [23]. The EQE is defined as the number of carriers produced per photon. It is a function of λ , directly governed by the amount of light absorbed by Si and can be written as

$$\text{EQE} = \frac{J_{ph}}{e} \frac{h\nu}{P_{in}} \quad (2.6)$$

or sometimes it is referred to an incident photon conversion efficiency [23].

The optical losses then refer to the reflected light out from the Si absorber and parasitic light absorption by other materials that do not contribute to photo-current generation such as metal contact. Primarily, light loss by reflection is dominant and it could be minimised by adopting a reflective rear metal contact for internal reflection [40], by applying anti-reflection coating [50], and by texturing the front surface of Si with the micro/nanostructure. Surface texture on the front surface is proven to be a robust solution to reduce light reflection by promoting forward light scattering, neighbouring light reflection, and light entrapment by total internal reflection. The topic on Si texturisation and details on mechanism as mentioned can be found separately in published review in ref. [32], which is a part of this project.

Table 2.3 compares the J_{sc} and PCE of conventional Si p-n and graphene/Si solar cells with different types of textures and anti-reflection coating. From the table, we can learn that Si microstructures such as cones, hillocks and pyramids remain as a better choice for improving J_{sc} . In conventional p-n junction solar cells, J_{sc} as high as $\sim 40 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ is obtained for typical PCE around 19–20% [51,52]. Since p-n junction is formed by diffusion of dopant, the presence of surface texture does not affect much on the junction formation. This means J_{sc} for the conventional Si p-n junction solar cell can be improved without interfering with another merit such as V_{oc} and FF. However, it is a grave limitation for graphene/Si solar cell because current technology is limited to the wet transfer of graphene on the target substrate, instead of deposition or growth. In ref. [53], even if they used the Si micro pyramids texture on the front surface and obtained high $J_{sc} = 40.8 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, the graphene/Si junction is however located at the flat surface of rear Si. Their device structure is IBC. If they wet transferred graphene on Si micro pyramids, the junction will not be uniform and the contact will be insignificant.

Except for the work in ref. [53], the remaining graphene/Si solar cells in Table 2.3 are formed by wet transfer of CVD graphene on the textured Si surface. Figure 2.4(a) and (b) show the schematic and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of graphene transferred on Si nanowires from ref. [59]. They obtained $J_{sc} = 11.24$ mA/cm², $V_{oc} = 0.503$ V, FF = 50.6%, and PCE = 2.86%. For this performance, they claimed that it is delivered by ~20% of the designated area of 0.283 cm² because of the sparse distribution of nanowires on the surface. The remaining area that is not in contact most probably will act as recombination spots so that it is believed that their poor FF is due to the severe surface recombination by unpassivated nanowires.

Table 2.3 Comparison between different types of Si textures and anti-reflection coating on J_{sc} and PCE of conventional and graphene/Si solar cells

Junction	Si texture	Anti-reflection coating	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	PCE (%)	Ref.
Si p-n	Microcones	Al ₂ O ₃ , SiN _x	40.60	19.90	[51]
Si p-n	Microhillocks	Al ₂ O ₃ , SiN _x	39.90	18.90	[52]
Si p-n	Micropyramids	SiN _x	36.70	18.20	[54]
Si p-n	Nanowires	none	16.82	5.30	[55]
graphene/Si	Micropyramids	SiO ₂	40.80	14.10	[53]
graphene/Si	Quantum dots	none	39.60	16.17	[15]
graphene/Si	Nanoholes	none	38.86	10.30	[56]
graphene/Si	Microholes	none	31.56	10.40	[57]
graphene/Si	Micropillars	none	17.33	4.35	[58]
graphene/Si	Nanowires	none	11.24	2.86	[59]

Figure 2.4(c) and (d) show the schematic and SEM image of graphene that was transferred on Si micro holes from ref. [57]. They obtained $J_{sc} = 31.56$ mA/cm², $V_{oc} = 0.52$ V, FF = 63.4%, and PCE = 10.4%. Besides the higher J_{sc} (indicating that holes are better than wires) from previously discussed, micro-sized hole in this work enable higher FF because of the larger border provides more contact with graphene. This leads to a pre-conclusion that; if graphene could completely wrap the Si structures, improvement in J_{sc} is possible to be achieved without sacrificing the FF.

Figure 2.4 (a) Schematic, and (b) SEM image of graphene on Si nanowires [59]. (c) Schematic, and (d) SEM image of graphene on Si micro holes [57]

Textured Si surface broke the crystal bonds in the lattice. If broken bonds are not passivated, they would contribute to lower minority carrier (photo-excited carrier) lifetime. In the case of flat Si surface before texturisation, the effective minority carrier lifetime, τ_{eff} , can be estimated by

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{eff}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{bulk}} + \frac{2S_{eff}}{t} \quad (2.7)$$

where τ_{bulk} is the minority carrier lifetime in bulk Si, S_{eff} is the effective surface (front and rear) recombination velocity, and t is the thickness of Si substrate [60]. If the front surface is textured, τ_{eff} now is may be estimated by

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{eff}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{bulk}} + \frac{S_{front} (A_1/A_2) + S_{rear}}{t} \quad (2.8)$$

where S_{eff} is separated into S_{front} and S_{rear} . At the front textured surface, area enhancement factor which is the ratio of the front textured area (A_1) in respect to the projected planar area (A_2) is taken into account and it varies greatly for different types

of structures. This explains the need for mitigation in reducing S_{front} in order to prolong the τ_{eff} so that it will be successfully diffused and collected at the contact before recombination occurred.

In conventional Si p-n junction solar cell, the textured surface can be effectively passivated either by SiO₂, silicon nitride (SiN_x), or Al₂O₃ that also serves as an anti-reflection coating. However, this cannot be applied to the case of graphene/Si solar cell because the anti-reflection coating needs to be thick normally in the range of 100–150 nm for optimum effect in reducing reflection [60]. The thick coating as an interlayer between graphene and Si in principal is a metal-oxide-semiconductor capacitor with no current flow across the junction. To overcome this problem, one could opt for chemical passivation especially by terminating Si bond with methyl [61]. Nonetheless, chemical passivation is not the main focus of this thesis and will not be further elaborated.

2.5 Reduced Graphene Oxide as an Alternative for Graphene

The rGO perhaps is an answer for unfeasibility that is faced by wet transferred CVD graphene on textured Si surface. As we discussed before, wet transfer of graphene film on textured Si surface will result in the least effective junction area than anticipated, while at the same time non-contact textured Si area becomes a culprit for severe surface recombination. If rGO could wrap the Si textures and could create a MS junction as good (or better) as graphene, then this research is already one-step forward and this is definitely a meaningful research work. The big question now is: how good rGO could offer compared to graphene? How much rGO differs from graphene in terms of material properties? Is there a lead to convince how capable rGO in wrapping the textured Si surface, and how would they perform specifically as a solar cell?

Firstly, rGO, as its name suggests, is a reduced form of GO. Low-cost exfoliation of graphite by aqueous-phase exfoliation does oxidise and then exfoliate bulk graphite, producing a mass volume of defected graphene known as GO [33]. GO sheet has a defected graphene lattice by substitution and attachment of various oxygen

functional groups on its basal plane and edges [35]. Details of electrical properties of GO will be discussed in the next chapters; but in short, the presence of oxygen functional groups significantly lowers its conductivity compared to crystalline graphene. Finally, the reduction of GO into rGO improves the conductivity which is depending on the degree of reduction and remaining defects on its lattice. In order to evaluate graphene and rGO performance as a transparent conductor, the figure of merit (dimensionless) for optoelectronic performance in the form of a ratio between σ_{dc} and σ_{op} is commonly used

$$\frac{\sigma_{dc}}{\sigma_{op}} = \frac{188.5}{R_{sq} (T_{op}^{-1/2} - 1)} \quad (2.9)$$

where σ_{dc} is the direct current conductivity (or just referred as σ), σ_{op} is the optical conductivity, R_{sq} is the sheet resistance, and T_{op} is the optical transmission at $\lambda = 550$ nm [62]. For the pristine graphene without dopant, we return to its fundamental dc and optical conductivity as a 2D material

$$\frac{\sigma_{dc}}{\sigma_{op}} = \frac{\sigma_{2D,dc}}{\sigma_{2D,op}} = \frac{4e^2/h}{e^2/4\hbar} = \frac{8}{\pi} = 2.55 \quad (2.10)$$

which is supposed to be 2.55. This is valid if we consider the ballistic carrier transport in graphene when its E_F located at Dirac point. If graphene is doped, quasi E_F is now displaced from Dirac point and the carrier is transported by drift mechanism as occurred in the 3D crystalline lattice. This modifies the figure of merit into

$$\frac{\sigma_{dc}}{\sigma_{op}} = \frac{\sigma_{3D,dc}}{\sigma_{2D,op}} = \frac{en\mu}{e^2/4\hbar} = \frac{4\hbar n\mu}{e} \quad (2.11)$$

which returns back to Drude's relationship for the conductivity of 3D material. Depending on carrier concentration, n and mobility, μ after doping, the practical σ_{dc}/σ_{op} for graphene would be in the broad range of 11–330 [62]. For comparison, 30–400 nm thick ITO that typically with $R_{sq} = 5\text{--}60 \Omega/\square$ and T_{op} more than 85%, the σ_{dc}/σ_{op} is then around 450 which is very high and justifies how good it is as a transparent

conductor regardless of being pricey [63]. The trade-off between optical transparency and conductivity in rGO film indeed is very challenging. This is because continuous rGO film is built from stacking of individual rGO sheets in the least controllable manner, where most of time rGO film needs to be sufficiently thick in order to ensure it to be a continuous stack of rGO sheets.

At present, the highest σ_{dc}/σ_{op} for rGO film is reported in ref. [64] at the value of 28.5 after being doped with silver nanoparticles. Figure 2.5(a) and (b) show the photo of large area graphene and rGO film on polyethylene terephthalate (PET) by roll-to-roll production. Large area graphene is from ref. [65], where σ_{dc}/σ_{op} is obtained as high as 116. Meanwhile, rGO film is from ref. [66], where they obtained the maximum σ_{dc}/σ_{op} at only 2.4.

Figure 2.5 (a) Large area graphene film on 35-inch PET [65]. (b) Large area 25 cm width rGO film on PET [66]. Both graphene and rGO are obtained by roll-to-roll production

At present, the two highest PCE reported for rGO/Si solar cell; $\sim 4\%$ by Han et al. [67] and 5.2% by Lee et al. [68] as shown their devices in Figure 2.6(a) and (b) respectively. Han et al. fabricated rGO/Si solar cell by spray-coating GO dispersion onto the n-Si substrate, then proceeded to 10 minutes' thermal reduction in a hydrogen atmosphere at 800 °C [67]. Without providing details on the merit of performance, they obtained $I_{sc} \sim 2.7$ mA and $V_{oc} \sim 0.45$ V for the PCE $\sim 4\%$ (read from J-V plot, but it looks like their reported cell area is not correct). We could notice that J_{sc} from this

rGO/Si solar cell is relatively low compared to graphene/Si and conventional Si p-n junction solar cells that have been discussed in the previous section.

The origin of low J_{sc} most probably coming from low transparency of rGO (high parasitic light absorption) and untextured Si surface. Lee et al. fabricated rGO/Si solar cell by spin-coating chemically-reduced rGO on randomly textured Si micro pyramids [68]. They obtained $J_{sc} = 23.3 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, $V_{oc} = 0.44 \text{ V}$, and $\text{FF} = 50.78\%$ for those $\text{PCE} = 5.2\%$. In comparison for rGO/Si solar cell fabricated using flat Si, they obtained $J_{sc} = 18.26 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, $V_{oc} = 0.41 \text{ V}$, $\text{FF} = 39.61\%$, and $\text{PCE} = 2.96\%$.

Figure 2.6 (a) Photo of rGO/Si solar cell with front metal fingers and busbar [67]. (b) Photo of rGO/Si solar cell utilising random textured Si micro pyramids with top metal electrode [68]

Figure 2.7(a) and (b) show the coating of rGO film after it was spin-coated on randomly textured Si micro pyramids by Lee et al. [68]. The individual rGO looks like a wrinkled sheet, covering the sidewalls of pyramids. Figure 2.7(c) compares the front surface reflectance of rGO on flat and textured Si surfaces. Before deposition of rGO film, reflectance (at $\lambda = 550 \text{ nm}$) for flat Si was 30%. After the texturisation, the value dropped to only 9%. As shown in Figure 2.7(d), the presence of Si micro pyramids significantly increased the J_{sc} , while at the same time improved the V_{oc} and FF. However, due to the random texturisation of those micro pyramids, large and tall pyramids are having a higher probability to be coated, causing non-perfect and even none-wrapping of smaller neighbouring pyramids. If the texture can be made in a uniform manner, perhaps wrapping quality could be upgraded and possibly adjusted the performance of rGO/Si solar cell to a more satisfying value. There was no σ_{dc}/σ_{op}

reported from both works because once rGO deposited on Si substrate, T_{op} can no longer be measured.

Figure 2.7 SEM images of rGO sheets cover on random Si micro pyramids after spin-coating: (a) Top view; (b) side view. (c) The reflectance of flat and textured Si surfaces. (d) J-V characteristic of rGO on flat and textured Si solar cells [68]

2.6 Graphene Oxide as an Interlayer in Solar Cell

This is the last section in this chapter, where it is necessary to understand the function of GO as a hole transport layer in graphene/GO/Si solar cell. Yang et al. have fabricated graphene/GO/Si solar cell as shown in Figure 2.8(a) [69]. By employing GO interlayer with large E_g , it imposed a high barrier for moving an electron in the conduction band of Si into graphene. Meanwhile, the hole is allowed to cross the junction with an insignificant barrier. Thus, under illumination, the photo-excited hole in n-Si is allowed to drift-diffuse into graphene but not for the electron. This selective carrier transport prohibits carrier recombination, therefore resulting in higher FF as shown in Figure 2.8(b). The thickness of GO plays a decisive factor in determining the

performance of the solar cell, where a thick layer of it causes excessive parasitic resistance, while a thin layer would not be sufficient for the mechanism to work. They found 2.4 nm thick GO is optimum as a hole transport layer and around four times of improvement are measured for V_{oc} , FF and PCE as shown in Figure 2.8(c). This thickness is not far from optimum thickness suggested for MIS graphene/insulator/Si solar cell, which is 1.5 nm for SiO₂ [17], 1.5 nm for hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) [70], 1.7 nm for hafnium dioxide (HfO₂) [71], and 2.0 nm for molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) [72]. This means that a slightly thick GO interlayer serves both functions as a hole transport and a tunnelling insulator in suppressing interface recombination.

Figure 2.8 Graphene/GO/Si solar cell: (a) Schematic device structure. (b) Comparison in light J-V plot. (c) Comparison in term of V_{oc} , J_{sc} and PCE between a device with and without GO interlayer [69]

Due to the alterable properties of GO by the degree of reduction, researchers might find the different optimum thickness of GO in graphene/GO/Si solar cell. Jiao et al. found the optimum thickness of GO interlayer to be at 3.5 nm [73]. Considerably thick GO is allowed because it is annealed at 200 °C, which increases its conductivity and results in greater photovoltaic performance. The conductivity of GO increased due to increasing conductive carbon sp^2 domains after annealing. Therefore, originally GO

that offers function as a hole transport layer and tunnelling insulator can be further exploited by altering the conductivity of its film, to another optimum point where a trade-off between parasitic resistance and FF improvement is in balance.

So far, we have learned that there is an indefinite conclusion when considering either we should totally replace the use of graphene with rGO (discussed in the previous section), or we can opt for tuneable GO reduction to serve several functions; as a hole transport, tunnelling insulator, and transparent conductor (discussed in this section). The key for this puzzle probably lies within the path of further understanding the GO itself. If the process allows, a possible structure of rGO/GO/Si solar cell should be investigated. It could be either fabricated in two-step of deposition rGO on GO/Si or perhaps by controlling the reduction GO/Si into rGO/GO/Si. The methods toward this ambition are described in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Flowchart

Figure 3.1 shows the flowchart for the first experimental work. The scope is about synthesising graphene oxide (GO) dispersion and characterisation of the GO film. Starting with aqueous phase exfoliation of graphite, obtained GO dispersion is drop-casted on a glass substrate to form a thin film. The main electrical characterisation by Hall effect measurement is conducted to extract the properties of GO film.

Scope 1: Synthesis of GO dispersion and characterisation of GO film

Figure 3.1 Research flowchart for experimental work within the first scope

Figure 3.2 shows the flowchart for the second experimental work. The scope is about investigating the behaviour of GO/n-Si (metal-semiconductor) MS junction after the reduction of GO into reduced graphene oxide (rGO). Synthesised GO is drop-casted on the n-Si substrate and then annealed in nitrogen gas (N₂) at varied temperatures. Following, contacts are deposited for main electrical characterisation by 2-point probe current-voltage (I-V) measurement.

Scope 2: Investigation of junction behaviour after reduction GO into rGO

Figure 3.2 Research flowchart for experimental work within the second scope

Figure 3.3 shows the flowchart for the third experimental work. The scope is about fabrication and characterisation of rGO/n-Si solar cell. At first, microstructure texture is designed and simulated its optical characteristic. Desired design is selected to texturisation and then the sample is deposited with electrodes for a solar cell. Following, GO is drop-casted and annealed into rGO to complete the device. Main I-V measurement under 1-sun illumination is done to obtain the photovoltaic performance of rGO/n-Si solar cell.

Scope 3: Fabrication and characterisation rGO on textured Si solar cell

Figure 3.3 Research flowchart for experimental work within the third scope

3.2 Method of Fabrication

3.2.1 Synthesis of Graphene Oxide and its Film

GO was synthesised by the improved Hummers method [34]. First, 3 g of graphite flakes (grade 3061, Asbury Carbons) were mixed with 18 g of potassium permanganate powder. Then, the mixture was added into a solution made of 95 wt.% of sulfuric acid and 85 wt.% of phosphoric acid at mixing ratio of 360:40 ml, producing slight exothermic oxidation. Next, this mixed solution was heated at 50 °C on a hot plate and stirred mildly at 300 rpm using a magnetic stirrer for 18 hr. Here, a slurry mixture of oxidised graphite showed a change in its colour to dark brown. To stop the

oxidation, the solution was cooled down to the $T = 300$ K and then poured into 400 ml of cooled de-ionised (DI) water mixed with 30 ml of 30 wt.% hydrogen peroxide. When the colour of the mixture turned into dark yellow, this resulted in GO solution to be centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 1 hr to separate the precipitation and supernatant. The precipitation was subjected to 3 times' washing in a mixture of 20 wt.% hydrochloric acid and DI water (volume ratio 1:1) to remove residual potassium salt. Finally, GO was dispersed in DI water at the concentration of around 2 mg/ml. Details are provided in Appendix B and C. The synthesised GO dispersion was used to form a thin film on a glass substrate as shown in Figure 3.4(a) and (b). To obtain wet GO film, GO dispersion was drop-casted onto glass and left dried naturally for 24 hours. To obtain dried GO film, the film was subjected to heat treatment (HT) at 200 °C in the oven for 60 min. The sample was introduced from room temperature to 200 °C oven with confined ambient air.

Figure 3.4 (a) Organic-cleaned glass substrate in a petri dish before drop-cast of GO dispersion. (b) Drop-casted GO on a glass substrate as a film before and after HT

3.2.2 Fabrication of Graphene Oxide on Silicon Diode

The GO dispersion was drop-casted onto 1x1 cm² n-type Si substrate. The substrate was prepared from 725 μm-thick Si (100) wafer with a resistivity of 0.8–1.2 Ωcm. Prior to the drop-casting, the substrate was subjected to ultrasonic-assisted organic cleaning in acetone for 5 min and isopropyl alcohol (IPA) for another 5 min. Then, it was immersed in 10% hydrofluoric acid for 30 sec to remove native oxide. The drop-casted GO was left to dry at 50 °C on a hotplate. A circular GO thin film

with a diameter of 0.9 cm was formed. The sample was loaded into the furnace and the furnace was purged and soaked with purified N₂ for 5 min prior to the annealing. The GO was reduced by annealing at a varied temperature from 100 to 700 °C for 30 min. The heating rate was set 100 °C/min and the duration of annealing counted after the temperature was stabilised at the set value. Figure 3.5 shows the model of GO reduction. Applied heat in inert N₂ induced removal of oxygen functional groups through the formation of carbonaceous species such as CO₂ and CO [35]. Removal of oxygen functional groups results in defective graphene lattice. After 30 min annealing, indium-tin (In-Sn) dots around 0.2-mm diameter were deposited on rGO and n-Si to create ohmic contacts. The junction area was defined by the circular area of 0.636 cm².

Figure 3.5 Model of reduction of GO into rGO by a thermal method

3.2.3 Fabrication of Reduced Graphene Oxide on Silicon Solar Cell

The steps in fabricating Si inverted micro pyramids are described in Figure 3.6(a)–(f). First, a 525 μm-thick SiO₂/Si wafer was cleaved into pieces of 1x1 cm². The SiO₂ was 100 nm thick, thermally grown on n-type Si (100) which was having a bulk resistivity of 0.3–0.5 Ωcm. Each sample was then subjected to ultrasonic-assisted organic cleaning in acetone for 5 min and IPA for 5 min. The surface was treated with hexamethyl-disilazine prior to resist coating. Then, undiluted ZEP-520A was spin-coated on the sample at 3000 rpm for 60 sec, followed by a pre-bake on the hotplate at 180 °C for 5 min.

The square array was patterned using electron beam lithography (JEOL JBX-6300FS, 100 kV voltage and 5 nA current, 240 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ dose) for the area of 0.5x0.5 cm^2 . After exposure, the sample was developed in xylene for 60 sec, rinsed in IPA for 30 sec, and post-baked in the oven at 180 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min. The sample with exposed SiO_2 after pattern development was immersed in 10% hydrofluoric acid for 6 min and rinsed in DI water. After that, the ZEP-520A residual was removed by methyl ethyl ketone and organic cleaning.

Figure 3.6 Steps in fabricating Si inverted micro pyramids: (a) Coating the ZEP-520A on SiO_2/Si . (b) Exposure and pattern development. (c) Etching the exposed SiO_2 . (d) Removal of ZEP-520A. (e) Etching the Si in TMAH/IPA. (f) Removal of SiO_2

The exposed Si sample was etched in a mixture of 5 wt.% tetramethylammonium-hydroxide (TMAH) and 10 vol.% IPA at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 120 min. Figure 3.7(a) and (b) show the texturisation setup of Si using TMAH/IPA. During etching, the beaker was stirred at 300 rpm using magnetic stirrer. Beaker was sealed on the top in order to reduce the loss of TMAH/IPA by evaporation. The process begins with the dissociation of TMAH into TMA^+ and OH^- in water [32]. The OH^- and water are responsible for Si etching according to

Figure 3.8(a) to (d) describe the steps in fabricating solar cell of rGO on Si inverted micro-pyramids. Si sample with inverted pyramidal structures fabricated in the previous process was patterned and deposited with front Au and rear aluminium

(Al) electrodes using thermal evaporation. Contacts are then annealed in N_2 at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 min. Then, 2 mg/ml of GO dispersion was drop-casted on the top structure. To obtain rGO, the GO was thermally reduced in N_2 ambient for 30 min with a similar methodology described in Section 3.2.2. The annealing temperature was according to the best value concluded from the discussion in the second scope.

Figure 3.7 (a) Setup of Si surface texturisation using TMAH/IPA. (b) An enlarged view of texturisation with visible bubbles of H_2 from the chemical reaction

Figure 3.8 Steps in fabricating rGO on textured Si solar cell: (a) Textured Si as a substrate. (b) Deposition of front Au and rear Al electrodes. (c) Deposition of GO dispersion by the drop-cast method. (d) Annealing to reduce GO into rGO

3.3 Method of Characterisation

Table 3.1 provides a list of equipment for material and device characterisation that have been used throughout this project. UV absorption of GO dispersion in DI water was measured using UV spectroscopy to determine the bandgap, E_g . Optical reflectance from the Si surface was measured using UV-visible spectroscopy. Crystal condition of graphene's derivatives was determined using the vibrational technique by employing Raman spectroscopy. Details on Raman spectroscopy are provided in Appendix D.

Table 3.1 List of equipment, model, remark, and their occurrence in thesis chapter for material and device characterisation

Equipment	Model	Remark	Chapter
UV spectroscopy	AquaMate 8000	$\lambda = 200\text{--}400\text{ nm}$	4
UV-visible spectroscopy	Shimadzu UV-1800	$\lambda = 300\text{--}700\text{ nm}$	6
Raman spectroscopy	WITec alpha300R	$\lambda = 514\text{ nm}$	4,5,6
Surface profiler	KLA Tencor D-100	-	4,5,6
Metallurgical microscope	Olympus BX51M	Low mag. view	5,6
FESEM	FEI Helios NanoLab G3	High mag. view	6
Hall-effect measurement	Ecopia HMS-3000	$T = 300\text{ K}$	4,5,6
I-V measurement	Agilent B1500A	$T = 300\text{ K}$	4,5,6
Solar simulator	Newport LCS-100	STC 1-sun	5,6

The thickness of the film was measured using a surface profiler. Low and high magnification metrology inspections were done using a metallurgical microscope and field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), respectively. The 4-point probe Hall effect measurement was carried out in van der Pauw configuration at room temperature of $T = 300\text{ K}$. Figure 3.9 shows the photo of van der Pauw configuration for contacting the dried GO film. Details on Hall effect measurement are provided in Appendix E. The 2-point probe I-V measurement also was carried out at room temperature. The light source was provided by solar simulator according to standard test condition (STC).

Figure 3.9 The van der Pauw configuration for Hall effect measurement

Air mass (AM) zero is the irradiance at extraterrestrial with an integrated power density of 136.6 mW/cm^2 . Upon reaching the terrestrial level, light is scattered by particles in the atmosphere depending on the value of AM. The AM1.5G has an integrated power density of 100 mW/cm^2 and it represents 1-sun for STC of the solar cell. Newport LCS-100 simulated the AM1.5G using Xenon lamp. The measurement was done at $T = 300 \text{ K}$. Details on solar simulator are provided in Appendix F.

3.4 Design and Optical Simulation of Silicon Texture

The Si inverted micro pyramids are 2D designed and their optical characteristic is simulated by finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method using Lumerical FDTD. The refractive indexes and permittivity of Si are in accordance to Palik's handbook [74]. The structure is defined by three parameters: width (W), depth (D) and space (S) as shown in Figure 3.10(a). The W is studied in the range of $1\text{--}10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, while the D follows the value of W by the relation of

$$D = (W / 2) \tan 54.7^\circ \quad (3.2)$$

which is constrained by the angle of 54.7° between $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ in Si crystal [32]. The S for the Si inverted pyramid configured in a square array is studied in the range of $0\text{--}3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3.10 (a) Schematic of inverted pyramidal structures. (b) The configuration of the FDTD region with PML and periodic boundaries

Figure 3.10(b) shows the simulation configuration in Lumerical FDTD. The 2D boundary conditions are defined by the periodic boundary for both upper and lower x -axis, while a perfectly matched layer (PML) boundary for both upper and lower y -axis. The plane wave in the UV-visible range ($\lambda = 300\text{--}700$ nm) is used as a light source. The plane wave is defined by the transverse magnetic field (TMF) and the transverse electric field (TEF) mode to simulate the unpolarized light.

3.5 Extraction of Data from the Measurement

3.5.1 Band Gap Calculation of Graphene Oxide

The Tauc plot analysis is extracted from the UV absorbance in the form of $(\alpha hv)^{1/n}$ versus hv to estimate the E_g of GO. The relationship between the absorption coefficient, α and hv is expressed by

$$(\alpha hv)^{1/n} = A(hv - E_g) \quad (3.3)$$

where A is the absorption constant [75]. It is considered that $n = 1/2$ represents the direct band transition.

3.5.2 Material Properties from Hall Effect Measurement

The sheet resistance, R_{sq} of the GO film is obtained by the 4-point probe in the van der Pauw configuration. Consider assigning each corner of the square as A, B, C, and D as shown in Figure 3.8, the resistance of R_{AC} and R_{BD} thus can be obtained by applying current, I through it. The R_{sq} is related to R_{AC} and R_{BD} by

$$\exp\left[-\pi \frac{R_{AC}}{R_{sq}}\right] + \exp\left[-\pi \frac{R_{BD}}{R_{sq}}\right] = 1 \quad (3.4)$$

$$R_{sq} = \frac{\pi}{\ln 2} \left(\frac{R_{AC} + R_{BD}}{2} \right) f \quad (3.5)$$

Here, f is the numerical factor based on the ratio of vertical/horizontal which is proven useful to extend measurement to the arbitrary-shaped sample [76]. The conductivity, σ is a bulk property of the film which is related to the R_{sq} and thickness, t by

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R_{sq} t} \quad (3.6)$$

Consider an x -directional current, I_x from one type of charge carrier flows from $+V_x$ to $-V_x$. Under an applied perpendicular magnetic field, B_z , the charge carrier in motion will experience Lorentz force and being deflected into y -directional, thus building the transversal electric field [6]. In the steady-state, I_y is zero and Hall voltage which is equivalent to V_y is measured from the GO film. The majority carrier concentration, n and carrier mobility, μ can be extracted from V_y and V_x by

$$V_y = \frac{I_x B_z}{en t} \quad (3.7)$$

$$n = \frac{I_x B_z}{e V_y t} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\mu = \frac{I_x}{eV_x nt} \quad (3.9)$$

where e is the elementary charge with a value of 1.6×10^{-19} C [6].

3.5.3 Determination of Schottky Barrier Height

Details on MS junction formation can be found in Appendix A. Consider an example of rectifying Schottky junction formed by intimate contact of metal and n-type semiconductor with metal work function, Φ_M is higher than semiconductor work function, Φ_S at $T = 300$ K. The I-V characteristic of the diode is described as

$$I = I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{eV}{\eta kT}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (3.10)$$

where I_0 is the reverse saturation current and η is the diode ideality factor ($\eta = 1$ for the ideal diode) [23]. The I_0 in MS junction may be expressed as

$$I_0 = A_j A^* T^2 \left[\exp\left(\frac{-e\Phi_B}{kT}\right) \right] \quad (3.11)$$

where A_j is the junction area and A^* is the Richardson constant for semiconductor (112 A/cm²K² for n-type Si). Both Equations (3.10) and (3.11) can be expressed in terms of current density for a given A_j as

$$J = J_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{eV}{\eta kT}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (3.12)$$

$$J_0 = A^* T^2 \left[\exp\left(\frac{-e\Phi_B}{kT}\right) \right] \quad (3.13)$$

Schottky barrier height which is experienced by an electron moving from metal into semiconductor denoted by Φ_B is formed approximately

$$\Phi_B = |\Phi_M - X| \quad (3.14)$$

where X is the electron affinity of semiconductor which is equivalent to 4.05 eV for Si [6]. Effective barrier, Φ_i imposed to move an electron in E_c into metal is then

$$\Phi_i = \Phi_M - \Phi_S = \Phi_B - kT \ln \frac{N_c}{N_d} \quad (3.15)$$

where N_c is the density of states function in the E_c , while N_d is the donor concentration in n-Si [6]. The depletion width, W_d and maximum electric field, E_{\max} from the metal-semiconductor junction then may be expressed as

$$W_d = \left[\frac{2\epsilon_s \epsilon_0 \Phi_i}{eN_d} \right]^{1/2} \quad (3.16)$$

$$|E_{\max}| = \frac{eN_d W_d}{\epsilon_s \epsilon_0} \quad (3.17)$$

where ϵ_s is the dielectric constant for semiconductor (11.7 for Si) and ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space equivalent to 8.85×10^{-14} F/cm [6].

3.5.4 Determining the Photovoltaic Performance of Solar Cell

Consider the junction is exposed to illumination with photon energy $h\nu > E_g$, absorbed photon excites hole minority carrier in valence band for the n-type semiconductor. Due to the gradient of n within the depletion region, photo-excited hole drift-diffuses into metal even without an external applied electric field. When the source of illumination is absent, photo-excited carriers may eventually recombine (electron-hole recombination) and they are being annihilated for the junction to revert

into their thermal equilibrium condition. For the light I-V, assuming there are no losses in the photo-generated carrier, the magnitude of short circuit current, I_{sc} is equivalent to photo-generated current, I_{ph} . The open circuit voltage, V_{oc} can be expressed as [23]

$$V_{oc} \approx \frac{\eta k T}{e} \ln \left(\frac{I_{ph}}{I_0} + 1 \right) \approx \frac{\eta k T}{e} \ln \left(\frac{I_{ph}}{I_0} \right) \quad (3.18)$$

$$V_{oc} \approx \frac{\eta k T}{e} \ln \left(\frac{I_{ph}}{A_j A^* T^2} \right) + \frac{\eta \Phi_B}{e} \quad (3.19)$$

The determination of fill factor (FF) and power conversion efficiency (PCE) can be referred to Equation (2.3) and (2.4), respectively. Along with mentioned parameters, a complete Schottky diode also includes series resistance, R_s and shunt resistance, R_{sh} [23]. Thus, I-V for Schottky diode under illumination more accurately can be expressed as follows

$$I = I_0 \left[\exp \left(\frac{eV - IR_s}{\eta k T} \right) - 1 \right] + \frac{V - IR_s}{R_{sh}} - I_{ph} \quad (3.20)$$

A parasitic loss by R_s may be contributed from several factors especially bulk material resistance and contact resistance. High R_s results to lower FF and PCE. Meanwhile, R_{sh} represents parallel resistance that blocks the reverse direction of current in the device. High R_{sh} then indicates low photo-excited carrier recombination. High R_{sh} results in higher FF and PCE in the fabricated solar cell.

CHAPTER 4

SYNTHESIS OF GRAPHENE OXIDE AND EFFECT OF TRAPPED WATER IN ITS FILM

4.1 Introduction

Wet graphene oxide (GO) film is known to have trapped water [77,78], which might alter the electrical properties of the film but the identification on it is still uncertain and often neglected. To dry out trapped water in GO film, heat treatment (HT) was carried out by mild temperature heating at 200 °C in the oven for 60 min. In Chapter 2 previously, experimental work by Jiao et al. has been discussed, which is using GO as a hole transport layer in graphene/GO/Si solar cell [73]. They have demonstrated that annealing of graphene/GO/Si at 200 °C results in a drastic improvement in open circuit voltage and fill factor of the solar cell compared to the one without annealing. In this chapter, direct characterisation of GO film before and after HT will unveil why such improvement could exist in annealed graphene/GO/Si solar cell.

4.2 Characterisation of the Synthesised Graphene Oxide

The UV absorbance of the synthesised GO dispersion is shown in Figure 4.1. The absorbance peak at 5.4 eV ($\lambda = 230$ nm) is an absorbance by the remaining conjugation in oxidised graphene by $\pi-\pi^*$ transition, while a noticeable small shoulder around 4.1 eV ($\lambda = 300$ nm) can be ascribed as $n-\pi^*$ transition of carbonyl groups [35]. Taking the intercept of the tangent line, two values were obtained at 3.5 eV and 4.5 eV. The value of 3.5 eV represents the $n-\pi^*$ transition due to the oxygen localised states (carbonyl groups), while the value of 4.5 eV represents the bandgap, E_g of GO sheet which is resulted from $\pi-\pi^*$ transition.

Figure 4.1 UV absorbance (left) and Tauc plot (right) of the synthesised GO dispersion in de-ionised water

The Raman spectra for the synthesised GO sheet in comparison to exfoliated multi-layer graphene (MLG) on SiO₂/Si substrate are shown in Figure 4.2(a) and (b). It could be identified that the peak intensity ~1340 cm⁻¹ is for D band, while ~1600 cm⁻¹ is for G band. They came from the GO sheet. Meanwhile, intense G band ~1577 cm⁻¹ and 2D band ~2720 cm⁻¹ are identified coming from the reference MLG. The origin of G band is from E_{2g} in-plane phonon at the zone centre Γ point in crystalline graphite material, while D band appeared when the disorder was introduced in the lattice [79,80].

Figure 4.2 (a) Scan area of the sample. (b) Raman shift from GO and reference MLG with indicated map intensity before HT

Oxidation of crystalline sp^2 carbon in GO resulted in a frequency shift of G band approximately $+23\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and broadening its width compared to the reference MLG. The frequency shift, in this case, can be related to the changes in chemical bond and its symmetry in oxidised sp^2 carbon in GO compared to the pristine sp^2 carbon in MLG. In other words, a rise in D band shifts the G band to the $+23\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [79]. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) for G band of GO is 70 cm^{-1} , which is significantly larger than FWHM of MLG which is 17 cm^{-1} . Meanwhile, FWHM of D band of GO is 90 cm^{-1} . Large FWHM of D and G band indicates that the crystalline sp^2 carbons in GO is small, presented with a large amount of disorder after the introduction of oxygen functional groups to its plane and edges. The intensity ratio of D/G band (I_D/I_G) was determined to be 0.967.

Peak $\sim 2720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the 2D band that was observed in MLG from the second order Raman scattering was also hardly noticeable from GO sheet. The 2D band for MLG, in this case, consist of two collided peaks; they are known as D_1 (smaller peak) and D_2 (prominent peak at $\sim 2720\text{ cm}^{-1}$) [80]. This suggests that the exfoliated MLG was considerably thick with 10 layers of graphene or slightly more. Those 2D band which is the second order of zone-boundary phonons almost disappeared after the oxidation and make it not possible to determine the number of layers in the individual GO sheet.

The Raman spectra for synthesised GO sheets and reference MLG after HT are shown in Figure 4.3(a) and (b). The GO sheets appeared darker and the contrast of GO sheets was lowered against the SiO_2/Si substrate and the reference MLG. There was no frequency shifting observed in both D and G band of GO sheet after the film was subjected to the HT. The I_D/I_G , however, was adjusted to a slightly higher value at 0.976, indicating increases of disorder in the lattice. As the difference was negligibly small, it suggested that applied HT was affecting oxidised graphene lattice minimally without inducing major removal of oxygen functional groups. Within $100\text{--}250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, minor de-oxygenation of epoxides, COOH , C=O , and C-OH and formation of C=O and C-O were expected to be occurred [81]. Applied HT at $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ does not repair the broken lattice in GO so that there was no disappearance in D band and no appearance of 2D band in the Raman spectra.

Figure 4.3 (a) Scan area of the sample. (b) Raman shift from GO and reference MLG with indicated map intensity after HT

Figure 4.4(a) and (b) show the photo and schematic of GO film on the glass before and after HT. Continuous and uniform GO film on glass was effortlessly obtained due to the hydrophilicity of the GO dispersion by the attached oxygen functional groups [82]. The film was originally brown in colour, then it later transformed into a darker colour after subjected to HT.

Figure 4.4 Photograph (left), thickness profile (middle) and schematic illustration (right) of GO film: (a) Before HT. (b) After HT

The change in colour was related to the minor de-oxygenation by of epoxides, COOH, C=O, and C-OH as suggested in ref. [81] that has been discussed earlier. The water was expected to be trapped within a thick stack of GO sheets upon drop-casting and natural drying onto the glass. This trapped water was evaporated and left the slightly reduced GO sheet to stack each other as shown in the illustration. The average thickness, t of GO film before HT was 296 nm, while after HT the value was slightly reduced to 230 nm.

4.3 Effect of Heat Treatment on Electrical Properties of Graphene Oxide Film

The current-voltage (I-V) characteristic under sweep current, I for the GO film before and after HT is shown in Figure 4.5(a) and (b) respectively. In GO film before HT, there was a ‘step-like’ conductivity (or capacitive) with two distinguished series resistance, R_s . Take an example of forward sweep I from -0.5 to 0.5 μA , high R_s region was found within a range of -0.5 to 0 μA and 0.3 to 0.5 μA with the value of $5.67 \times 10^8 \Omega$. Low R_s region was within 0 to 0.3 μA with the value of $3.00 \times 10^7 \Omega$. Reversing the sweep direction of applied I from 0.5 to -0.5 μA , the hysteresis loop was created and the values of both R_s were maintained. The ‘step-like’ and hysteresis conduction from the film was eliminated after subjected to HT. The region of low R_s disappeared and it gave a linear characteristic with R_s of $5.71 \times 10^8 \Omega$, which was comparable to the high R_s region found previously in film before HT.

After the oxidation, large $E_g = 4.5 \text{ eV}$ was introduced on the GO sheet. Insulating domains with E_g induce variable-range-hopping (VRH) transport mechanism, where local non-oxidised region remained as conductive sp^2 carbon domain and responsible for conductivity. Oxidised region acted as a barrier for carrier transportation, so that majority carrier needed to hop over the barrier from a conductive sp^2 domain to another [83,84]. Supposedly, the VRH should result in a single linear I-V characteristic at a constant temperature. The ‘step-like’ and hysteresis found in GO film before HT showed the contribution of trapped water within the film, giving a temporarily high conductivity.

Figure 4.5 I-V characteristic after forward and reverse sweep current on GO film: (a) Before HT. (b) After HT

The sheet resistance, R_{sq} and conductivity, σ for the GO film before and after HT under sweep I are shown in Figure 4.6(a) and (b) respectively. Since the difference in t between the film before and after HT was small, the trend in σ was simply inverted to the trend of R_{sq} . The majority carrier in both GO film before and after HT is hole.

Figure 4.6 Properties of GO film before and after HT under sweep current: (a) Sheet resistance. (b) Conductivity. (c) Concentration. (d) Mobility

The majority carrier concentration, n and mobility, μ under sweep I are shown in Figure 4.6(c) and (d) respectively. The perpendicular magnetic field, B was kept constant at 0.884 T. There was a threshold value of I around 100 nA before the R_{sq} and σ gave readable values with minimised fluctuation. Current below this point most probably consumed to compensate the depleted carrier within the film. Taking the measurement window from 100 nA to 10 μ A, the average and standard error (SE) of measured properties of the film are tabulated in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Properties of GO film before and after HT from sweep current during Hall effect measurement

	R_{sq} ($\times 10^5 \Omega/\square$)		σ (S/cm)		n ($\times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$)		μ (cm^2/Vs)	
	Average	SE	Average	SE	Average	SE	Average	SE
Before	4.21	2.03	0.58	0.19	2.72	0.74	466.36	125.10
After	0.96	0.35	1.02	0.21	5.72	2.20	351.09	40.16

According to Table 4.1, the value of conductivity from dried GO film was slightly higher than wet GO film. This is because the minor de-oxygenation by HT was increased the value of n in dried GO film. Trapped water in wet GO film in another point gives a higher average value of μ (with the higher SE) compared to the dried GO film. Since a raise of n in dried GO film was in a higher magnitude compared to the high μ in wet GO film, thus the final conductivity of dried GO film was simply higher than wet GO film. Comparison in SE suggests that the fluctuation in μ from wet GO film was more pronounced due to the carrier transportation assisted by trapped water.

At constant $I = 1 \mu\text{A}$, the changes in R_{sq} , σ , n , and μ of the GO film within sweep B are shown in Figure 4.7(a) to (d), respectively. The properties of the GO film after HT was found to be stable within sweep B rather than the film before HT. Large fluctuation of R_{sq} (thus affecting the extracted σ , n and μ) within sweep B indicated the presence of inhomogeneities and multi-carrier conduction [76]. The average and SE of measured properties of the film were tabulated in Table 4.2.

Figure 4.7 Properties of GO film before and after HT under sweep magnetic field: (a) Sheet resistance. (b) Conductivity. (c) Concentration. (d) Mobility

Table 4.2 Properties of GO film before and after HT from sweep magnetic field during Hall effect measurement

	R_{sq} ($\times 10^5 \Omega/\square$)		σ (S/cm)		n ($\times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$)		μ (cm^2/Vs)	
	Average	SE	Average	SE	Average	SE	Average	SE
Before	1.74	0.48	0.66	0.19	3.92	1.00	452.71	118.59
After	0.59	0.05	0.77	0.04	4.15	0.71	359.35	44.07

According to Table 4.2, the value of conductivity from dried GO film still higher than the value from wet GO film. This was tally with data described in the previous Table 4.1. Dried GO film has a higher n due to minor de-oxygenation, while wet GO has a higher μ due to the trapped water. Similarly, the fluctuation in μ from wet GO film was more pronounced due to the carrier transportation assisted by trapped water.

Figure 4.8(a) and (b) compare the relationship of μ - n in GO film before and after HT, including the effect of the depleted carrier as previously discussed. As the n was increased, supposedly μ should be lowered to remain to obey the Drude's relation of conductivity. The GO film after HT did show the tendency to follow the fitting line of μ - n , while the film before HT did not. This means that the μ in GO film before HT would remain extremely high at high n , thus resulting in abnormal yet temporarily high conductivity. The plots in Figure 4.8(c) and (d) show the relation of μ - σ in the films. The μ was vastly scattered in film before HT compared to the film after HT. As the conductivity depends on n rather than μ , they should be found clustered around the average value of measured σ .

Figure 4.8 Relationship of: (a) Mobility-concentration before HT. (b) Mobility-concentration after HT. (c) Mobility-conductivity before HT. (d) Mobility-conductivity after HT

The fitting line in the μ - n plot in Figure 4.8(a) and (b) suggest the dependency of μ on n was similar for both GO film before and after HT. This empirical determination was expected to hold validity for the general case of GO film, where the

σ was controlled by n by means of thickening the layer or doping by adsorbates. The presence of trapped water conversely deviated from the μ - n fitting line, vastly scattered, did not follow Drude's formula, and could be concluded as coming from off-sheet carrier brought by trapped water.

4.4 Summary

In this chapter, GO dispersion was synthesised and the film was obtained by drop-casting on the glass. Mild temperature HT on the synthesised GO sheets increased disorder on the lattice by a little, indicating a small degree of de-oxygenation. The thickness of drop-casted GO dispersion as a continuous film was indeed reduced after the HT. Sweep current during I-V measurement showed that the film before and after HT was comparable in its resistance, except trapped water gave temporarily high conductivity in the film before HT. Hall effect measurement had detected the abnormality caused by trapped water, especially inconsistent reading during sweep B .

In general, a small degree of de-oxygenation by HT has increased the n at the cost of μ so that the σ was slightly increased. The μ - n relationship was observable from the film after HT, even conduction was dominated by VRH mechanism. Whereas the μ in film before HT did not show any tendency to follow the μ - n relationship, thus abnormally high σ was frequently measured during the presence of high μ . High μ may be concluded was coming from off-sheet carrier brought by the trapped water, instead of hole majority carrier in the GO sheets.

CHAPTER 5

INVESTIGATION ON TRANSITION DIODE PROPERTIES OF GRAPHENE OXIDE ON SILICON HETEROJUNCTION

5.1 Introduction

The intermediate state between insulating graphene oxide (GO) and conducting reduced graphene oxide (rGO) is basically a product of low-degree and incomplete reduction. In previous reports, lowly reduced GO was not an insulator, but it was a p-type conductor for hole transportation in the solar cell [73]. It is also significant to clearly understand how the parameters in the reduction process influence the electrical characteristics of an rGO/Si junction. The inconsistency in the reported rGO/Si diode parameters in some of the previous studies was possibly due to different rGO preparation condition [85–87]. The degree of reduction of rGO is best controlled by thermal annealing, where unique removal of certain oxygen functional groups can be done at a certain range of temperatures [81,88]. To pave a deeper understanding on the junction of GO/Si, rGO/Si and its transition state in between, probing at intervals of annealing temperature (AT) are necessary. In this chapter, thermal reduction and transition properties of GO into rGO by controlling the AT will be discussed. Deposited on Si, changes in junction properties are analysed during the transition of GO into rGO.

5.2 Characterisation of Graphene Oxide and Reduced Graphene Oxide Film

The GO sheets are expected to form a continuous film on the Si surface by their interconnection at polar oxygen functional groups [35]. The Si surface after native oxide removal was hydrophobic whereby the surface repelled water. By the assistance of high surface tension between GO droplet and bare Si surface, the diameter of circular GO film could be controlled to the desired 0.9 mm. Figure 5.1 shows the

device schematic and the surface morphology of the GO film on Si before and after annealing. The GO film after subjected to 100 °C annealing started to demonstrate colour change from brown to dark colour. As the AT increased, the film noticeably became distorted with observable boundaries and wrinkles. The lateral size of boundaries and wrinkles were in the range of several to hundreds of micrometres. The presence of boundaries and wrinkles, however, do not break the continuity of the film. They, unfortunately, might leave a slight degradation in electrical conductivity due to more scattering experienced by the majority carrier during drifting in the applied electric field.

Figure 5.1 Schematic of rGO/n-Si diode and surface morphology of the GO film after annealing from 100 °C to 700 °C

The thickness of deposited GO films on the Si surface before and after annealing at different AT is shown in Figure 5.2. The thickness of the GO film was approximately 236 nm and steadily reduced for a higher AT. After AT = 700 °C was applied, the thickness of GO film was reduced to 207 nm. The reduction of GO thickness can be explained by the removal of oxygen functional groups that decorating the basal plane and edges of graphene lattice. Higher temperature annealing of GO in inert N₂ release the oxygen functional groups and leave the graphene lattice defected and eventually lower film thickness.

Figure 5.2 Average thickness of drop-casted GO film on Si before and after annealing from 100 °C to 700 °C

The Raman shift from GO film is shown in Figure 5.3(a). We can identify the peak intensity of the D and G band at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Thermal reduction of GO does not induce shifting in the D and G band but change their relative peak intensity. Figure 5.3(b) shows the change in I_D/I_G with respect to the AT. Initially, GO has $I_D/I_G = 0.985$. After annealing, a slight increase in I_D/I_G was observed. The highest I_D/I_G value was 1.004 and obtained after AT = 700 °C. The increase in I_D/I_G indicates the increase of defective sites after the removal of oxygen functional groups from GO basal plane and edges. None of the blue or red shift was observed for the GO peaks in the Raman spectra before and after annealing.

Figure 5.3 (a) Raman shift from GO film before annealing. (b) The I_D/I_G ratio after annealing from 100 °C to 700 °C

The properties of the GO film were obtained by Hall effect measurement. GO was drop-casted on a glass substrate and was thermally reduced in a similar manner on Si substrate. Figure 5.4(a) to (c) show the majority carrier concentration, n , mobility, μ and conductivity, σ respectively of the GO film before and after annealing at different AT. The GO film before subjected to annealing is a p-type conductor with $n = 2.05 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 258.69 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, and $\sigma = 5.15 \text{ S/cm}$. Upon treatment at AT = 100–300 °C, the n (hole) increased exponentially and slightly reduced the μ (hole). This resulted in an increment in σ . Above AT = 400 °C, the GO film alternately showed n-type and p-type conduction. As shown by the data interpolation in the plots, transition in majority carrier in the film was found to be occurred around AT = 370 °C. Beyond the transition point, the n (electron) gradually decreased while the μ (electron) increased. This also resulted in an increment in σ , making the plot in Figure 5.4(c) seamless from initial 5.15 S/cm to the final 19.7 S/cm.

Figure 5.4 Hall effect measurement of GO before and after annealing: (a) Concentration. (b) Mobility. (c) Conductivity

The enhancement in film conductivity after annealing is an indicator of GO reduction (also can be studied by other techniques such as thermogravimetric analysis and differential thermal analysis). The observed increment in n (hole) below $AT = 400$ °C is attributed to the increment of available hopping sites within the film. The removal of oxygen functional groups was responsible for the reduction of potential barriers between the crystalline sp^2 carbon domains [89,90], thus increased the conductivity of the film. Tu et al. in their recent report have discussed conversion between hole and electron majority carrier in rGO at unique annealing temperatures [88]. They found that the conversion from p-type to n-type rGO started in the range of $AT = 300$ – 450 °C due to the predominant of electron donating groups (EDG) compared to the electron withdrawing groups (EWG). In Figure 5.4, within $AT = 100$ – 300 °C, the predominant on the film was electron withdrawing groups. Within $AT = 400$ – 700 °C, the predominant of either EDG or EWG was ceased to exist, thus the film alternately showed n-type and p-type conduction. Figure 5.5 shows the illustration of lattice and band diagram of GO for different AT. Besides increasing the number of available hopping sites, EWG and EDG respectively modulate the Fermi level, E_F of crystalline sp^2 graphene lattice. EWG withdraws electron from the crystalline sp^2 domain, thus increases the E_F value. The EDG simply works otherwise. Modulation of E_F supports the explanation of increased available hopping sites because of the increased density of states.

Figure 5.5 Illustration of GO lattice before and after annealing which indicates a predominant transition from EWG into EDG on crystalline sp^2 domains

In previous work on pristine graphene by Zhang et al., E_F was found to be not consistent across the sheet due to charge-donating impurities which were creating electron and hole puddles [91]. This case is similar to GO, except a large number of electron and hole puddles are created and potentially separated by attached oxygen functional groups. By potentially separating them into localised sites, the concept of predominant groups takes place and transition point can be regarded as a charge neutrality point. Extending the concept of predominant groups, the condition of the film can be classified into three, which are GO, hybrid rGO-GO after incomplete reduction at mild temperature annealing, and rGO.

5.3 Current-Voltage Characteristic of Diodes after Annealing

The semi-log current density-voltage (J-V) plots of GO/n-Si diode before and after annealing are shown in Figure 5.6. The current fluctuation was noticeable at low bias especially for the sample fabricated at low temperature. The current fluctuation diminished as the AT increased. The minimum point of current density was also observed to shift away from zero voltage.

The so-called zero offset voltage was determined and plotted as a function of AT in Figure 5.7(a). The sample made from unreduced GO showed negative voltage shift. As the temperature increased to 300 °C, the voltage shift became more positive. Annealing at higher temperature eliminated the voltage shift. The observed current fluctuation and offset voltage could be as a result of the trapped charges within the film [92,93]. Trapped water temporarily holds the charge and results to parasitic capacitance. The effect of the trapped charges became less significant after removal of trapped water and the removal of oxygen functional groups by the thermal reduction process. The current fluctuation of the sample prepared at low AT could also be associated with poor conductivity of GO film. After thermal reduction, the film conductivity has improved and subsequently minimised the current fluctuation.

Figure 5.6 Semi-log J-V plot of the GO/n-Si diode before and after AT

Carrier transport in the prepared sample was considered to follow the thermionic emission. The saturation current density, J_0 , Schottky barrier height (SBH), and diode ideality factor, η were extracted from the forward bias region of the J-V characteristics. Figure 5.7(b) and (c) show the extracted saturation current density and calculated SBH, respectively. The SBH decreased as the AT increased. As shown in Figure 5.7(d), the obtained result corresponded to the decrease of work function, Φ from 4.65 to 4.5 eV.

The difference in the calculated Φ was caused by the variation of the type of attached functional group and oxygen content [88,94]. In the case when the type of functional group is the dominant factor, the relationship between the change of Φ and AT became less straight-forward. This is because the occurrence and removal of EDG and EWG happen at a certain temperature. On the other hand, the Φ was shown to be reduced when the oxygen content was reduced after thermal reduction. Based on the obtained result, the Φ modulation observed in this experiment was speculated as a result of the reduction of oxygen content at the higher annealing temperature. Relating to the transition of predominance that occurred around AT of 370 °C, interpolation from Figure 5.7(d) gives Φ at charge neutrality point of 4.62 eV.

Figure 5.7 Changes in dark diode properties during annealing: (a) Offset voltage. (b) Saturation current density. (c) Schottky barrier height. (d) The work function of GO. (e) Ideality factor. (f) Rectification ratio

Figure 5.7(e) shows the calculated η as a function of AT. The high value of η was obtained from the sample prepared at low temperature. The η of the junction with unreduced GO was 12.97, far leaving the ideal diode of $\eta = 1$. The value of η decreased to 4.69 for AT = 400 °C. In an earlier report by Chen et al. on the fabricated graphene/n-Si Schottky junction, the value of η was also large, which the range was in between 4.89 and 7.69 [95]. Similar work by Sinha and Lee on graphene/n-Si diode suggested that the deviation from the ideal value, i.e, $\eta = 1$ was probably due to the defective interface and impurities-contained graphene [96]. The extreme value of η also hinted the formation of metal-insulator-semiconductor (MIS) junction instead of metal-semiconductor (MS) junction.

An ideal Schottky junction should exhibit rectifying behaviour. Rectification ratio is evaluated based on the ratio of forward current density to reverse current density. High rectification ratio can be achieved when a forward current is high and reverse current is low. Figure 5.7(f) shows the rectification ratio calculated from the current at ± 1 V. The ratio increased to 149 at 400 °C before decreasing at a higher AT. The sample prepared at 300 and 400 °C exhibited pronounced Schottky J-V characteristics. On the other hand, the sample prepared at 700 °C showed ohmic-like characteristics with a rectification ratio almost one.

The improvement of the rectification ratio is due to the improvement of GO film conductivity after thermal annealing. Poor film conductivity results in high series resistance and low forward current. The series resistance could be determined from the high forward bias region. In this region, the current is limited by the series resistance. Figure 5.8 shows the series resistance as a function of AT. The obtained trend was consistent with the result shown in Figure 5.4(c).

The trend in series resistance is directly related to the bulk film conductivity. Owing to the smaller series resistance, the magnitude of forward current became higher. As a result, the rectification ratio increased significantly. However, when annealing was done above 400 °C, the rectification ratio was shown to decrease. The sample prepared at 700 °C has a rectification ratio of 0.88. One of the possible explanations is the increase of reverse current due to the reduction of SBH at the higher

annealing temperature. At reverse bias operation, the SBH was further reduced because of the image force effect and/or modulation of E_F [97].

Figure 5.8 Series resistance of GO/n-Si diode before and after AT

Figure 5.9 shows the band diagram of the junction forward and reverse bias. Initially, at zero bias, the junction achieved thermal equilibrium by aligning E_F of rGO and n-Si. When the junction was forward-biased, the E_F of n-Si was shifted upward and the built-in potential, Φ_i was lowered. Electron eventually jumped over the potential barrier into rGO. Note that the biasing also tuned the position of E_F . At forward bias, the change of E_F did not significantly affect the electrical characteristics. The forward current is largely dependent on the applied voltage. At reverse bias, current is contributed by the carrier flow from the graphene to n-Si. The reverse biasing elevates the E_F and thus produces lower effective SBH.

Figure 5.9 Band diagram of the rGO/n-Si-junction in forward and reverse bias

The effect of image force also further reduced the effective SBH. In the sample prepared at a higher temperature, the SBH was reduced to 0.5 eV. At reverse bias, the SBH was further reduced to a certain point where the electron could easily overcome the potential barrier. As a result, the magnitude of reverse current has increased and the rectification ratio has degraded. The high temperature-annealed sample was also expected to have a higher number of free electrons owing to its lower Φ . More electrons were available to jump off the reduced SBH. In the case of the sample prepared at the lower annealing temperature, the modulation of the Fermi level gave less significant effect as the SBH was quite high. The effective SBH can still block most of the carriers in the GO from overcoming the potential barrier.

5.4 Summary

Thermal reduction of GO films into hybrid rGO-GO (100–400 °C) and rGO (500–700 °C) have provided the film with higher electrical conductivity. The GO and hybrid rGO-GO films were p-type, while rGO films were in transition between p-type and n-type conductor. The transition diodes of rGO-GO/n-Si junction were having a higher SBH compared to the rGO/n-Si diode because of a higher Φ in the rGO-GO film. The GO/n-Si and rGO-GO/n-Si diodes behaved as low rectifying MS diode.

The lowest value in η and the highest rectification ratio was found on the rGO-GO/n-Si diode after being annealing at 400 °C. Hence, this was the best-found temperature for the reduction of GO film. Even though the conductivity of rGO film increases linearly for every increase in AT, higher AT than 400 °C led the behaviour of rGO/n-Si diodes towards ohmic and it allowed significant current flow in applied reverse bias. As the consequence, the rGO/n-Si after annealed at 500–700 °C exhibited low rectification ratio and not suitable for the purpose of the solar cell.

CHAPTER 6

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF SILICON SOLAR CELL UTILISING REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE AND TEXTURED SURFACE

6.1 Introduction

An introduction on micro-scaled texture on Si surface is important to reduce light reflectance. In this chapter, the uniform pattern of Si inverted micro pyramids is designed, simulated and textured to be used as a substrate for solar cell fabrication. The optical characteristic of the Si inverted micro pyramids is simulated using a software package based on the finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method [98]. The texturisation is carried out using tetramethyl-ammonium-hydroxide (TMAH) and isopropyl alcohol (IPA) as described in Chapter 3. TMAH etches Si anisotropically with high etching rate in $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction, but very slow in $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction [99]. This creates pyramidal structures on Si (100) substrate. The additional IPA as a surfactant assists the production of more uniform pyramids texture [100].

Textured Si (T-Si) inverted micro pyramids are intended to lower light reflectance compared to flat Si (F-Si), and at the same time to increase surface area for junction formation with reduced graphene oxide (rGO). To obtain rGO/T-Si and rGO/F-Si junction, first graphene oxide (GO) dispersion is drop-casted on respective T-Si and F-Si substrate in a similar manner elaborated in previous Chapter 5. After that, GO is thermally reduced by $AT = 400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ into rGO. The coverage of rGO sheets should be further improved if it is uniform instead of random arrays of pyramidal textured structures are utilised. Increases in the contact area between rGO and T-Si are the key to improve both the optical and electrical concerns in achieving a highly efficient rGO/Si solar cell.

6.2 Light Reflectance from Silicon Inverted Micro Pyramids

The simulated average surface reflectance for the pyramid width, $W = 1\text{--}10\ \mu\text{m}$ with constant spacing, $S = 0\ \mu\text{m}$ is shown in Figure 6.1(a). Starting with $W = 1\ \mu\text{m}$, the average reflectance of unpolarized light was 19.6%. Increasing the W in this range did not significantly increase the reflectance for both transverse magnetic field (TMF) and transverse electric field (TEF). Maximum percentage of 21.8% was obtained for the parameter of $W = 10\ \mu\text{m}$ and $S = 0\ \mu\text{m}$. Figure 6.1(b) shows the average reflectance for the $W = 10\ \mu\text{m}$ with the range of $S = 0\text{--}3\ \mu\text{m}$. By increasing the S , both TMF and TEF showed high increment in average reflectance. Starting with 21.8% average reflectance for the unpolarized light, the value was increased to 31.4% for the $W = 10\ \mu\text{m}$ and $S = 3\ \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 6.1 Average reflectance in UV-visible by changing the parameter of Si inverted pyramid: (a) Width. (b) Space

The 9.6% difference between minimum 21.8% and maximum 31.4% reflectance in the search range of $W = 1\text{--}10\ \mu\text{m}$ and $S = 0\ \mu\text{m}$ was a trade-off for the simplicity in fabrication and larger surface area. During fabrication, the etching mask for a larger feature size would tolerate better with uncertain mask/substrate etching selectivity and undercut compared to the smaller feature size. As a result, the process would become more controllable and high uniformity in etched texture can be obtained. The one proceeded to fabrication was $W = 10\ \mu\text{m}$ and $S = 3\ \mu\text{m}$. Introducing this parameter, Si front surface area was increased by 43.2% compared to the original flat surface.

Figure 6.2(a) to (d) show the stages and schematic of etching Si inverted micro pyramid (random spots on the surface under 50x magnification). The starting substrate was the opened square window of SiO₂ mask on Si. The anisotropic etching of TMAH/IPA did not etch the array of exposed Si in a consistent manner. As shown in Figure 6.2(a) after 30 min etching, random start points of inverted pyramids were observed on Si surface. The etching continued for a prolonged period of 60 min and 90 min as shown in Figure 6.2(b) and (c) respectively until the array of Si inverted pyramids became apparent. Reaching due time of 120 min, the etching was stopped and then a complete uniform arrays of Si inverted micro pyramids were obtained as shown in Figure 6.2(d). The etching rate was slow most probably because of the addition of IPA. The function of IPA was to lower surface tension and liberating water particles in close vicinity to Si surface [101,102]. In return, except $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$, the overall etching rates in the rest of $\langle hkl \rangle$ were lowered [103,104].

Figure 6.2 Stages of obtaining Si inverted pyramids texture at different etching periods: (a) 30 min. (b) 60 min. (c) 90 min. (d) 120 min

The preferred TMAH/IPA etching for $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 110 \rangle$ resulted to etch stop at (111), creating 4 sidewalls of an inverted pyramid. Figure 6.3(a) shows the FESEM image of Si inverted micro pyramids array under 2000x magnification after removal of the SiO₂ mask. Because of Si etching undercuts under SiO₂, the S and W of the inverted pyramid were slightly off from the original lithography size [105]. The view of individual inverted pyramid sidewall at 8000x magnification is shown in Figure 6.3(b). The etching by TMAH/IPA has resulted in a clean and smooth Si (111) sidewall, with a sharp vertex. The undercut gave a slightly larger $W = 10\text{--}12\ \mu\text{m}$ at the

cost of smaller $S = 1\text{--}3\ \mu\text{m}$. Figure 6.4(c) shows the 6000x magnification, 60° angled view at cross-sectioned individual Si inverted pyramid. Since the inclination of sidewall was constrained at 54.7° , the depth, D of Si inverted pyramid was defined by the new $W = 10\text{--}12\ \mu\text{m}$. The D was verified to be in a range of $7.1\text{--}8.5\ \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 6.3 FESEM images of Si inverted pyramid: (a) Top view. (b) Top view in pyramid sidewall. (c) Tilted at 60° and a cross-sectional view

The comparison on surface reflectance within the UV-visible range between simulation and lab-measured is plotted in Figure 6.4 and tabulated in Table 6.1. The simulated average reflectance for the unpolarized light from flat Si was 45.9%, while for the inverted pyramid ($W = 10\ \mu\text{m}$, $S = 3\ \mu\text{m}$) is 31.4%. A high portion of light was reflected in UV wave ($\lambda = 300\text{--}400\ \text{nm}$) compared to the visible range ($\lambda = 400\text{--}700\ \text{nm}$) due to the intrinsic optical properties of Si.

Figure 6.4 Comparison between FDTD simulated and lab-measured light reflectance in UV-visible range from textured and flat Si surface

Table 6.1 Numerical comparison between FDTD simulated and lab-measured light reflectance in UV-visible range from textured and flat Si surface

	Reflectance simulation (%)			Reflectance lab-measured (%)		
	Flat	Pyramid	Difference	Flat	Pyramid	Difference
UV	54.3	39.6	14.7	62.9	12.9	50.0
Visible	37.5	23.1	14.4	44.0	7.9	36.1
UV-visible	45.9	31.4	14.5	53.5	10.4	43.1

The presence of Si inverted pyramid in simulation reduced the reflectance at 14.5% in average UV-visible range. In the case of actual lab-measurement, the average reflectance from flat Si was 53.5%. While the measured average reflectance from fabricated inverted pyramid was only 10.4%. The fabricated array of Si inverted pyramid has demonstrated a significant reduction in UV reflectance, where 50.0% was shaved for the UV wave. Approximately 43.1% reduction in surface reflectance was achieved by the textured Si inverted pyramid.

Both simulation and lab-measured reflectance have proven that Si inverted pyramid does reduce the light reflection. However, the comparison indicates that there is a huge difference between the anticipated value of simulation and lab-measured. For the flat Si, the difference in UV-visible reflectance was +7.6%. For the Si inverted pyramid, the difference in UV-visible reflectance was -21.0%. The reason for the huge difference is most probably due to several factors, which are: (1) The use of two-dimensional (2D) FDTD simulation instead of three-dimensional (3D) FDTD for the Si inverted pyramid; (2) Larger W and smaller S in fabricated inverted pyramid compared to the original design due to etching undercut; and (3) Irregularities spot on textured Si instead of perfectly uniform array on overall lithography area. The first factor is a common limitation since large feature consumes a lot of computational resources and time. 3D modelling and FDTD simulation for large area involve multiplication of mesh point, which store the material and geometrical information for solving electric and magnetic field propagation. As the consequence, up to our knowledge, 3D FDTD for microstructures never being reported. Relying on 2D FDTD, the simulated structure may ambiguously represent a V-groove texture instead of an inverted pyramidal structure.

Figure 6.5(a) and (b) show the illustration of reflectance suppression by Si V-groove texture (ambiguous 2D FDTD) and inverted pyramidal texture, respectively. Surface reflectance is reduced by neighbouring light reflection on inclined surfaces of Si (111) before travelling into bulk Si and being absorbed [32]. Since the structure is considerably far larger than incident light wavelength, the micrometre-scale changes in W do not induce a significant difference in reflectance. If a larger range of W is studied which is extending down to submicron and nanometre-scale, then significant difference on reflectance will be presented due to the involvement of phenomenal light scattering. Increasing the S for the micrometre-scale W , more light will incident on flat Si and they will be reflected out from the surface.

Figure 6.5 Illustration of optical loss reduction by promoting neighbouring reflection on Si: (a) V-grooves texture. (b) Inverted pyramids texture

The inverted pyramidal texture is basically built from two perpendicular V-groove. The presence of perpendicular inclined surfaces of Si (111) in inverted pyramidal texture increases the neighbouring light reflection, thus lowering the reflectance compared to V-groove. Referring to simulated and measured reflectance in Figure 6.4, we can observe a simple trend in the visible region where the reflectance of fabricated inverted pyramidal texture almost half the value of 2D FDTD.

6.3 Graphene Oxide on Silicon Inverted Micro Pyramids Texture

Figure 6.6(a) and (b) show the field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images of GO thin film on F-Si and T-Si substrate respectively under 2000x magnification. In the case of GO/F-Si, the GO sheets show a formation of a continuous film with micrometre-sized folds. While in the case of GO/T-Si, most of the locations showed a formation of GO layer only on the top surface of the inverted pyramidal structure. This created a suspended GO film with minimised contact area with Si surface. There was a very low occurrence of GO sheets to wrap the inner sidewalls as a continuous film. In this case, the coverage reached almost to the vertex of Si inverted pyramid, thus large contact area between GO and T-Si was achieved.

Figure 6.6 Top view FESEM images of: (a) GO/F-Si. (b) GO/T-Si with magnification at the inner sidewall

The thicknesses of GO and rGO films are shown in Figure 6.7(a). The average thickness of the GO film was approximately 296 nm, while the rGO film after the annealing was approximately 168 nm. The reduction process by annealing seemed to shrink approximately 128 nm of the original thickness. Raman shift from 514 nm laser on GO and rGO is shown in Figure 6.7(b). The I_D/I_G for GO was 0.985, while rGO was slightly higher at 0.994. Since the coverage of GO on T-Si by drop-cast resulting in suspended GO film (suspended rGO film after annealing), it needs to be improved to maximise the contact between GO and Si surface.

Figure 6.7 (a) Thickness of GO and rGO film. (b) Raman spectra of GO and rGO film after being annealed at 400 °C

By a different approach which is spin-coating of GO dispersion followed with drop-casting of another GO dispersion on T-Si, this resulted in improved contact. Upward force during spin-coating promotes the wrapping of inner sidewalls of Si inverted micro pyramids while following drop-casting ensures continuous coverage. After subjected to annealing at 400 °C, the sample was referred as rGO/T-Si (Imp). Figure 6.8 shows the device photograph and 10x magnification view from optical microscope on rGO/T-Si (Imp) surface. The surface appeared darker due to the reduction of reflectance by Si inverted micro pyramids and parasitic absorption by rGO film itself.

Figure 6.8 Photograph (left) and low magnification view (right) from optical microscopy on rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell

Figure 6.9(a) to (c) show Raman intensity mapping (area of $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}^2$) on rGO/F-Si, rGO/T-Si and rGO/T-Si (Imp) surface. Thermal reduction induced wrinkles on suspended GO film. If the contact between GO/T-Si can be improved so that none of suspended GO film left unchecked before thermal reduction, desired maximum and non-wrinkling rGO contact on T-Si can be obtained.

Figure 6.9 Large area Raman intensity mapping for D and G band on the surface of: (a) rGO/F-Si. (b) rGO/T-Si. (c) rGO/T-Si (Imp)

6.4 Diode's Characteristic and Photovoltaic Performance

Figure 6.10(a) shows the linear and semilog current-voltage (I-V) characteristic of the rGO/F-Si solar cell. Based on semilog dark I-V, linear

interpolation of current, I within 0–0.4 V gives the value of saturation current, $I_0 = 2.5 \times 10^{-7}$ A and diode ideality factor, $\eta = 3.99$.

Figure 6.10 Linear and semilog-scaled I-V plot of: (a) rGO/F-Si. (b) rGO/T-Si. (c) rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell under dark and light

From Hall effect measurement, the majority carrier concentration, n for the Si was measured to be $1.64 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (electron), with considerably high mobility, $\mu =$

1200 cm²/Vs due to the moderate value of n and gave the conductivity, $\sigma = 3.15$ S/cm. For the rGO film, the n was measured to be 5.65×10^{16} cm⁻³ (hole), having a relatively lower $\mu = 80$ cm²/Vs, and ultimately gave inferior $\sigma = 0.72$ S/cm compared to the Si.

The Schottky barrier height (SBH) was calculated to be 0.6 eV, while the work function, Φ was 4.61 eV. For those value of I_0 , approximately depletion width, $W_d = 1.79$ μ m and maximum electric field, $|E_{\max}| = 4.53 \times 10^4$ V/cm were created within Si from the interface. Upon illumination, the excess carrier was generated within Si and the I-V shifted to the positive side of bias voltage. Since the shape of I-V remained the same, the SBH did not change whether with or without a photo-excited carrier. Linear and semilog I-V for rGO/T-Si solar cell are plotted in Figure 6.10(b). Extraction of I_0 gave a similar value of 2.5×10^{-7} A, but with slightly higher $\eta = 4.02$. Identical I_0 results to the identical value of SBH and Φ to the case of rGO/F-Si diode. Lastly, linear and semilog I-V for rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell is shown in Figure 6.10(c). This was obtained: $I_0 = 2.5 \times 10^{-7}$ A and $\eta = 3.50$. The difference in the effective contact area caused the discrepancy in η between three devices. Most non-ideals were demonstrated by rGO/T-Si because of the minimum contact between suspended rGO film and T-Si surface. Thus, the promotion of inner sidewalls wrapping as observed in Figure 6.9(c) is the reason for the lowest η due to the largest effective contact area.

Figure 6.11 compares the photovoltaic performance indicator of rGO/F-Si, rGO/T-Si, and rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell. Both short circuit current density, J_{sc} and open circuit voltage, V_{oc} show an almost linear trend in improvement from rGO/F-Si to the rGO/T-Si (Imp) diode. This is a straightforward explanation where higher light absorption in T-Si gives a higher amount of photo-generated carrier in Si compared to the F-Si. Improvement in the contact area by the wrapping of inner sidewalls further increased the capability to collect the photo-generated carrier in Si. The larger contact area between rGO and Si resulted in higher V_{oc} , which was closely related to the J_{sc} according to the relationship described in Equation (3.18). Even the rGO/T-Si showed suspended rGO film as previously discussed in Figure 6.9(b), it produced a bit higher V_{oc} compared to the rGO/F-Si and it was most probably due to several isolated spots of sidewalls wrapping occurred across the whole surface area.

Figure 6.11 Comparison of photovoltaic performance of rGO/F-Si, rGO/T-Si, and rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell

The downside of having T-Si is on its relatively lower fill factor (FF) compared to the reference F-Si. Low FF in all devices suggests that the coverage of rGO film on either F-Si or T-Si does not passivate the Si surface, in contrast with GO as reported recently in ref. [106]. When no passivation scheme was adopted in this work, exposed and unsaturated Si dangling bond after the texturisation had increased the surface recombination and resulted in inferior FF [32]. In the case of rGO/T-Si where most rGO films were suspended on Si inverted pyramid, photo-generated carrier near inner Si sidewalls needed to drift-diffuse in the longer distance into rGO contact (on the border area), while at the same time they lost due to lack of surface passivation. Wrapping of rGO to the inner sidewalls in case of rGO/T-Si (Imp) collects the photo-generated carrier before they recombine, thus FF is slightly fixed to a higher value. Even though the observed trend of FF was not linear, the power conversion efficiency (PCE) as shown in Figure 6.11 maintained increasing due to the enhancement in both J_{sc} and V_{oc} . The highest PCE of 0.0052% was obtained by rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell. The PCE was relatively low compared to the conventional Si p-n junction solar cell due to the low conductivity of rGO and lack of surface passivation.

6.5 Culprit for Low Photovoltaic Performance and Future Mitigation

There is no doubt that the photovoltaic performance of all fabricated devices in this work were relatively low compared to the conventional Si p-n junction solar cells [42–45]. In order to raise the values, higher conductivity of rGO is required and that is possible to be tackled later on, as long as the pre-requirement of maximising the junction area on textured Si surface is contented. Low conductivity of rGO after thermal reduction at 400 °C still contains a large number of the insulating oxidised region as illustrated in Figure 6.12(a). As a consequence, parasitic series resistance for carrier transportation via conductive sp^2 domains are great enough to nullify the photo-generated current. Before successfully supplied to the load, the photo-generated carrier was lost on rGO film at close vicinity to the original location whereby it was generated.

Figure 6.12 (a) Illustration of insulating oxidised regions on rGO film and their elimination in case of complete de-oxygenation and defect-repair. (b) Projection of J_{sc} by considering lower effective junction area. (c) Projection of PCE by considering effective junction area and improvement in FF

In other words, the effective device area for collecting photo-generated carrier was significantly smaller than the designed 0.25 cm^2 . Further de-oxygenation and repairing of the sp^2 domain may increase the effective junction area by providing higher conductivity of rGO. Figure 6.12(b) shows the projection of J_{sc} if it is considered that the effective junction area was much smaller than the designed 0.25 cm^2 . In the case of conventional Si p-n junction solar cells that employed micro-sized texture for improved light absorption, the J_{sc} was typically around 40 mA/cm^2 as previously tabulated in Table 2.1. As the J_{sc} was directly indicating the value of photo-generated current according to Equation (2.5) without including any loss, so in this case, the effective junction area was only 0.2% from the designed 0.25 cm^2 which was approximately 0.05 mm^2 . Figure 6.12(c) shows the projection of PCE by considering the 0.2% effective junction area and anticipated FF in case of the device was well passivated. From the original value of FF around 20% as shown in Figure 6.11, better passivation strategy such as methyl termination of Si dangling bond [61] and others may increase the FF up to 80%. Optimistically, when the problem of effective junction area and low FF were addressed, rGO/Si solar might demonstrate PCE up to 10%.

6.6 Summary

The junction of rGO and T-Si was created by drop-casting GO droplet on Si inverted pyramid array, followed by annealing to induce thermal reduction. Drop-casting of GO droplet on T-Si has resulted in the formation of suspended GO film, covering the top of Si inverted pyramid array. Minimum contact of rGO and T-Si after the reduction has led to higher η in the fabricated rGO/T-Si diode compared to the reference rGO/F-Si diode. Alternative process with spin-coating of GO droplet on T-Si prior to drop-casting helps to fill GO sheets within sidewalls of Si inverted pyramid, improving the contact area, thus lowering the η . The PCE has shown an improvement for the rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell due to improvements in both J_{sc} and V_{oc} . Highest obtained PCE of 0.0052% by rGO/T-Si (Imp) solar cell could be possibly increased to an acceptable value if the low conductivity of rGO film being fixed and interface was well passivated.

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION

7.1 Main Outcome of this Project

This project was achieved its objective, where a large area coverage of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) film on the uniformly textured Si (T-Si) surface was demonstrated. It needs to be emphasised that the coating of rGO on either flat or T-Si surface made possible by harnessing the hydrophilicity of the synthesised graphene oxide (GO) dispersion. Prior to the thermal reduction, hydrophilic GO dispersion in de-ionised (DI) water contributes to the stickiness of continuous GO film after coated on hydrophobic oxide-removed Si. Uniform T-Si surface was proven good to reduce optical loss by a reduction in front surface reflectance and excellent to help conformal coating of GO film by simple approach of spin-coating and drop-casting methods. Improvement in photovoltaic performance by this proposed methodology was successfully verified.

7.2 Research Contributions

A thin film of GO prepared from GO dispersion in DI water should not be directly used for device fabrication. Although it is conductive, the conductivity is attributed by trapped water in the film which is not acting as a dopant for crystalline sp^2 but it brings off-sheet carriers. This is critical for the solar cell because it is a minority carrier device; excited minority carrier by light may recombine and annihilated. Heating at mild temperature is effective for drying out the water and it provides the actual GO film. Dried GO film can be used as a hole transport layer in graphene/GO/Si solar cell.

Instead of just a hole transport layer, GO film is investigated on its possibility to form rGO/GO/Si junction by controlling the reduction. Nevertheless, the results suggest that the possible structure is only rGO-GO/Si. The transition of GO into hybrid rGO-GO and finally into rGO is demonstrated by increasing the annealing temperature. However, type majority carrier of the film during transition also changed from p-type (hole majority) to n-type (electron majority) due to the dominance of either electron withdrawing or electron donating group. The situation led to the non-rectifying junction, except the one near charge neutrality point after subjected to the annealing temperature (AT) = 400 °C. To be fair, even the discussion distinguished the film as GO, rGO-GO and rGO for different AT, still the boundary of that classification is not obvious. It can be concluded that rGO/Si after AT = 400 °C is the best among the studied AT range of 100–700 °C, exhibiting the most ideal metal-semiconductor diode characteristic.

Concerning on Si substrate, T-Si surface offers lower light reflectance and larger contact area for junction formation with rGO. Wrapping of GO sheets on T-Si surface can be easily achieved by spin-coating and drop-casting GO dispersion on T-Si. Applying AT = 400 °C on the sample provides rGO/T-Si solar cell. It is marked as rGO/T-Si (Imp) during the discussion which is referring to the improved method in obtaining wrapping of GO. The trend of enhancement in short circuit current density and open circuit voltage are presented after the introduction of T-Si and improved rGO contact strategy. It is a concrete decision that wrapping of rGO sheets on inner sidewalls of T-Si is a promising feature that answer both current and voltage limitations in designing high-efficiency graphene/Si solar cell. The power conversion efficiency of 0.0052% measured from rGO/T-Si solar cell can be further improved by increasing the conductivity of rGO film.

7.3 Direction of Future Works

There are several things that should be noted for future research works. Next study should adopt the wrapping of GO on T-Si as a hole transport layer, then separately deposit graphene or highly reduced-doped rGO film on top of GO/T-Si.

After the problem of low rGO conductivity is solved, re-characterisation of the solar cell performance should be done. At this stage, it is almost necessary to do periodic characterisations for several days and weeks to evaluate the stability and degradation rate of the junction. Simultaneously, other batches also need to be prepared to study the photovoltaic performance of a solar cell under lower illumination than the standard test condition. Both investigations on ageing and low incident power are the next important things to be understood because of the apparent performance after fabrication is insufficient to advise the feasibility of this material for a complex integration of heterojunction.

Figure 7.1 shows the contribution of this work within the overall efforts on improving the efficiency of Si heterojunction solar cell. As mentioned, future works should consider the suggestion of using doped graphene or highly conductive rGO film on top of the GO/T-Si substrate. Following that, researchers may investigate another potential material for more complex integration of heterojunction.

Figure 7.1 Findings of this work within overall efforts on improving the efficiency of Si multiple- heterojunction solar cell

Another potential material for more complex integration of heterojunction can be referred to other two-dimensional semiconductors, such as transition metal dichalcogenides, thin films III-V and II-VI semiconductors, dyes, organics, and perovskites. More discussions on performance, cost of functioning and processing technology for each heterojunction are necessary in order to build a highly efficient, miniaturised and affordable solar cell.

The state of the art single-junction Si solar cell has achieved efficiency above 26% due to the minimisation of recombination losses. The concept of multiple-junction and Si heterojunction with advanced materials such as graphene and its derivatives encourage next works to exceed Shockley-Queisser limit of 33.3% efficiency without incurring significant cost in heterojunction materials. The finding in this thesis is important because it creates a bridge between established knowledge of marketed device to the future concept of multiple heterojunction and even tandem solar cell configuration.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Publications based on the main scopes of this thesis:

1. Abdullah, M. F. and Hashim, A. M. Review and Assessment of Photovoltaic Performance of Graphene/Si Heterojunction Solar Cells. *J. Mater. Sci.*, 2019. 54(2): 911-948.
ISI indexed, Q2, impact factor 2.993 (2017)
2. Abdullah, M. F. and Hashim A. M. Design of Optimum Rear Passivated Submicron Al Corrugation in Very Thin Textured Silicon Back-Contact Back-Junction Solar Cell for Absorption Enhancement up to Near-Infrared Region. *J. Photon. Energy*, 2018. 8(1): 014501.
ISI indexed, Q2, impact factor 2.157 (2017)
3. Abdullah, M. F. and Hashim, A. M. Improved Coverage of rGO film on Si Inverted Pyramidal Microstructures for Enhancing the Photovoltaic of rGO/Si Heterojunction Solar Cell, *Mater. Sci. Semicond. Process.* (accepted, in press).
ISI indexed, Q2, impact factor 2.593 (2017)
4. Abdullah, M. F. and Hashim, A. M. Design and Fabrication of Uniform Array Micro-Scaled Si Inverted Pyramid for Low UV-Visible Reflectance, *Sains Malaysiana* (accepted, in press).
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Other publications related to this thesis during studentship:

1. Abdullah, M. F., Alghoul, M. A., Naser, H., Asim, N., Ahmadi, S., Yatim, B. and Sopian, K. Research and Development Efforts on Texturization to Reduce the Optical Losses at Front Surface of Silicon Solar Cell. *Renew. Sustain. Energy. Rev.*, 2016. 66: 380-398.
ISI indexed, Q1, impact factor 9.184 (2017)
2. Rahmasari, L., Abdullah, M. F., Md Zain, A. R. and Hashim, A. M. Silicon Nanohole Arrays Fabricated by Electron Beam Lithography and Reactive Ion Etching. *Sains Malaysiana* (accepted, in press).
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ISI indexed, Q2, impact factor 1.775 (2017)
2. Abdullah, M. F. and Hashim, A. M. Synthesis of Graphene Oxide and Effect of Trapped Water in Graphene Oxide Film, *J. Electron. Mater.* (under review).
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Conference presentations based on the scopes of this thesis:

1. Abdullah, M. F., Abd Rahman, S. F. and Hashim, A. M. Investigation on Transition Diode Properties of rGO/GO/n-Si Heterojunction. *Nanotech Malaysia*. May 7-8, 2018, Kuala Lumpur.
2. Abdullah, M. F., Abd Rahman, S. F. and Hashim A. M. Synthesis of Graphene Oxide and Effect of Trapped Water in Its Film. *Nanotech Malaysia*. May 7-8, 2018, Kuala Lumpur.
3. Abdullah, M. F. and Hashim, A. M. Reflectance Characteristics of Textured Silicon Surface Modeled by FDTD Method. *Malaysia-Japan Joint International Conference*. September 5-7, 2016, Kuala Lumpur.

Other conference presentation related to this thesis during studentship:

1. Rahmasari, L., Abdullah, M. F., Md Zain, A. R. and Hashim, A. M. Si Nanohole Arrays Fabricated by Electron Beam Lithography and Reactive Ion Etching. *Nanotech Malaysia*. May 7-8, 2018, Kuala Lumpur.

APPENDIX A Formation of Metal-Semiconductor Junction

This section and the followings will introduce the basic facts on MS junction that is necessary to be understood in order to relate with the findings in this thesis. The prerequisite for this section is knowledge on the quantum theory of solid that is available in textbooks. The fundamentals such as the formation of allowed and forbidden electron energy bands in a semiconductor crystal, the statistical distribution of electron among the allowed energy levels and so forth are not discussed. Figure A.1(a) shows the energy levels in metal and semiconductor before forming the junction. Metal work function, Φ_M is equivalent to its Fermi level, with respect to the vacuum level, E_0 . E_0 represents free-electron energy level outside the material for both metal and semiconductor. Meanwhile, Φ_M represents the highest occupied electron energy state at $T = 0$ K in a metal.

Figure A.1 (a) Indication of several energy levels in isolated metal and semiconductor. (b) Creation of depletion region upon intimate contact. (c) Energy band diagram for Schottky junction for electron majority carrier, and (d) Schottky junction for hole majority carrier in a semiconductor

For the semiconductor's Fermi level, E_{FS} is positioned somewhere in between conduction band, E_c and valence band, E_v depending on doping level and type of majority carrier. In order to determine the position of E_{FS} , it needs to be considered either thermal-equilibrium electron concentration, n_0 or thermal-equilibrium hole concentration, p_0 . Assuming Boltzmann approximation ($E - E_{FS}$) \gg kT is valid, the position of E_{FS} offset from E_c can be estimated by

$$E_c - E_{FS} = kT \ln(N_c / n_0) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where N_c is the effective density of states (DOS) function in the E_c . Previously, N_c is obtained from the density of allowed electronic states in E_c

$$N_c = 2 \left(\frac{2\pi m_n^* kT}{h^2} \right)^{3/2} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where m_n^* is the DOS mass of electron and N_c is approximately $2.8 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for Si at $T = 300 \text{ K}$. Similarly, offset of E_{FS} from E_v can be estimated by

$$E_{FS} - E_v = kT \ln(N_v / p_0) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where N_v is the effective DOS function in the E_v , that is obtained from the density of allowed electronic states in E_v

$$N_v = 2 \left(\frac{2\pi m_p^* kT}{h^2} \right)^{3/2} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where m_p^* is the DOS mass of hole and N_v is approximately $1.04 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for Si at $T = 300 \text{ K}$. In an intrinsic semiconductor, E_{FS} has located around $(E_c - E_v)/2$ or the middle of the bandgap, E_g because of

$$n_0 p_0 = N_c N_v \exp[-E_g / kT] = n_i^2 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

in which, n_i is the intrinsic concentration that is always constant for a given semiconductor material and temperature. In n-type semiconductor with a given donor concentration, N_d , complete ionisation by temperature gives $N_d \gg n_i$, so that $n_0 \approx N_d$. Similarly, for the case of p-type semiconductor with a given acceptor concentration, N_a , complete ionisation gives $N_a \gg n_i$ and $n_0 \approx N_a$. This eventually substitutes Equations (A.1) and (A.3) into

$$E_c - E_{FS} = kT \ln(N_c / N_d) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$E_{FS} - E_v = kT \ln(N_v / N_a) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

These explained for the case of an extrinsic semiconductor, Φ_s which is equivalent to E_{FS} moves to either lower or higher energy level in respect to E_0 depending on N_a and N_d . Another property which is semiconductor electron affinity, X is not varied for different value of N_a and N_d . It is defined by the offset of E_c in respect to E_0 and the value of X for Si is 4.05 eV . Upon an intimate contact between a metal and a semiconductor with $\Phi_M > \Phi_S$, metal depletes electron in semiconductor's side as illustrated in Figure A.1(b) and the energy band diagram is shown in Figure A.1(c).

APPENDIX B Synthesis of Graphene Oxide

Figure B.1 shows the illustration for synthesising GO by Improved Hummer method. This initially produces a slurry GO (after cleaning of composition from residual potassium salt). Slurry GO then can be further diluted with DI water for specific desired concentration.

Figure B.1 Synthesis of GO dispersion by improved Hummer method

Figure B.2 shows the photos of synthesised GO before and after centrifugation. The early dispersion prior to cleaning is centrifuged to separate heavy potassium salt as precipitation apart of GO dispersion. After three times of cleaning and centrifugation, desired GO dispersion is now obtained and ready for further action such as dilution and reduction.

Figure B.2 Photos of synthesised GO dispersion before and after centrifugation

Figure B.3 shows the GO sheets before and after reduction. Individual GO sheet appears as transparent white and easily distinguished by its contrast.

Figure B.3 GO sheet as prepared and after reduction by thermal or chemical

Figure A.4 shows the morphology of continuous GO film on glass. The film appears darker after the reduction. The thickness of film can be measured by creating a border between the area covered by GO and the one which is not.

Figure B.4 Magnified view of GO film on glass and thickness measurement

APPENDIX C Chemistry of Graphene Oxide

The Hummers method uses a combination of potassium permanganate and sulfuric acid. Though permanganate is a commonly used oxidant (e.g. dihydroxylations), the active species is, in fact, diamanganese heptoxide.

This dark red oil is formed from the reaction of potassium permanganate with sulfuric acid. The bimetallic heptoxide is far more reactive than its monometallic tetraoxide counterpart and is known to detonate when heated to temperatures greater than 55 °C or when placed in contact with organic compounds. The most common source of graphite used for chemical reactions, including its oxidation, is flake graphite, which is a naturally occurring mineral that is purified to remove heteroatomic contamination. As such, it contains numerous, localized defects in its π -structure that may serve as seed points for the oxidation process. Many of the earliest structural models of graphite oxide proposed regular lattices composed of discrete repeat units. The most recent models of graphite oxide have rejected the lattice-based model and have focused on a nonstoichiometric, amorphous alternative. Certainly, the most well-known model is the one by Lerf and Klinowski (Figure C.1).

Figure C.1 Variations of the Lerf-Klinowski model indicating ambiguity regarding the presence (top) or absence (bottom) of carboxylic acids on the periphery of the basal plane of the graphitic platelets of graphite oxide

Both graphite oxide and graphene oxide are electrically insulating materials due to their disrupted sp^2 bonding networks. Because electrical conductivity can be recovered by restoring the π -network, one of the most important reactions of graphene oxide is its reduction. The product of this reaction has been given a variety of names, including reduced graphene oxide, chemically-reduced graphene oxide, and graphene. The two are often confused but the structural differences can be significant, making the use of separate terms appropriate. Graphite oxide contains myriad oxide functionalities (predominately alcohols and epoxides), but retains a stacked structure similar to graphite, albeit with much wider spacing (6–12 Å, depending on the humidity) due to water intercalation. In discussing the reduction of this material, however, we must distinguish ‘graphene oxide’ from graphite oxide. Chemically, graphene oxide is similar, if not identical, to graphite oxide, but structurally it is very different. Rather than retaining a stacked structure, the material is exfoliated into monolayers or few-layered stacks. The surface functionality (particularly in basic media) greatly weakens the platelet-platelet interactions, owing to its hydrophilicity. A variety of thermal and mechanical methods can be used to exfoliate graphite oxide to graphene oxide, though sonicating and/or stirring graphite oxide in water are the most common. Sonicating in water or polar organic media, despite being much faster than mechanical stirring, has a great disadvantage in that it causes substantial damage to the graphene oxide platelets. Rather than having a mean size on the order of several microns per side, the dimensions are diminished to several hundred nanometers per side, and the product contains a considerably larger distribution of sizes. The oxidation process itself also causes breaking of the graphitic structure into smaller fragments. The maximum dispersibility of graphene oxide in solution, which is important for processing and further derivatization, depends both on the solvent and the extent of surface functionalization imparted during oxidation; to date, it has been found that the greater the polarity of the surface, the greater the dispersibility. dispersibilities are typically on the order of 1–4 mg/ml in water. It is believed that sonication results in near-complete exfoliation of the graphite oxide.

Chemical reduction is certainly the most common method of reducing graphene oxide, but it is by no means the only method. Results have been presented on the thermal exfoliation and reduction of graphite oxide. Rather than using a chemical reductant to strip the oxide functionality from the surface, it is possible to create thermodynamically stable carbon oxide species by directly heating graphite oxide in a furnace. A notable effect of thermal exfoliation is the structural damage caused to the platelets by the release of carbon dioxide. Approximately 30% of the mass of the graphite oxide is lost during the exfoliation process, leaving behind vacancies and topological defects throughout the plane of the reduced graphene oxide platelet. Defects inevitably affect the electronic properties of the product by decreasing the ballistic transport path length and introducing scattering sites. Despite these structural defects, however, bulk conductivities of 1000–2300 S/m have been previously measured, indicating effective overall reduction and restoration of the planes’ electronic structure. Although it has not been studied to date, these defects may also have an effect on the mechanical properties of the product, compared to a chemically-reduced sample.

APPENDIX D Raman Spectroscopy of Graphene

Light interactions with matter can provide rapid, quantitative, non-destructive, characterisation of materials. Raman spectroscopy is based on inelastic scattering arising from electron-phonon interactions. Incoming electromagnetic waves interact with quantised lattice vibrations by polarizing the electron distributions in atomic bonds. In other words, the incident light causes the electron cloud to oscillate, which in turn causes the atoms to vibrate. This interaction with the lattice vibrations absorbs or augments the energy of the electrons depending on the available vibrational modes and quantum selection rules. When the electrons finally relax and scatter a photon, it will have a different energy than the incident photon. The resulting change in frequency, known as the Raman shift, provides characteristic information about the atomic constitution, bonding character, and impurity concentration of the material.

Figure D.1 illustrates the Raman scattering mechanism. Diagrammatically, we see that the incident light is absorbed by the molecule or bond, promoting it into a virtual excited state. Statistically, the system will return to the initial state in a radiative process known as Rayleigh scattering, however, some probability ($\sim 10^{-7}$) exists that it will relax to a different state by coupling to an optical phonon. If the final state has more energy than the ground state (a phonon is created), the emitted photon is red shifted (Stokes shift). Less likely, is a transition from which the electron cloud gains energy (a phonon is annihilated) and emits a blue shifted photon (anti-Stokes shift). Since the probability of phonon creation and annihilation is determined by Bose-Einstein statistics, the relative intensity of the shifts is proportional to

$$\frac{I_s}{I_{a-s}} \propto \frac{n+1}{n} = \exp\left(\frac{E_p}{k_B T}\right) \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where n is the number of phonons with energy, E_p . Therefore, barring certain cases where quantum selection rules or photoluminescent interference precludes its use, Stokes Raman is preferable due to the higher signal intensity. Finally, if the incident excitation energy coincides with an electronic transition, then the process is resonant and the intensity is enhanced.

The electron-phonon interaction is analogous to the classical damped, forced, harmonic oscillator, where the damping energy is related to the polarizability, and the driving force is equivalent to the oscillating electric field created by the incident light. For perturbatively damped systems such as this, the resulting peaks approach Lorentzian functions, with line widths that are inversely proportional to the phonon lifetime. The peak intensity is a complex function of the polarizability, which itself is time-dependent and a function of the vibrational mode.

Figure D.1 Diagram of the Raman scattering process. Incident radiation causes the electron cloud to oscillate, thereby promoting the system into a virtual excited state. The system typically relaxes back to the initial state, emitting a photon of equal energy, in a process known as Rayleigh scattering. In rare cases, the oscillating electron cloud will lose (gain) energy by coupling to an allowed vibrational mode of the system and scatter a red (blue) shifted photon

Raman spectra are plotted as the intensity of the scattered light versus the Raman shift ($E_i - E_f$) in inverse wavenumbers (cm^{-1}). Lasers are commonly used as excitation sources because they are monochromatic and their intensity makes up for low scattering probabilities. A very efficient notch or edge filters are used to block the Rayleigh scattered light so that high-gain photodetectors can be used to capture low-intensity Raman features.

Raman is a low probability process that is best suited to study surfaces like graphene. Surface sensitivity can be tuned somewhat by the choice of incident radiation, while quantum selection rules determine the coupling cross-sections for interactions between specific incident wavelengths and the vibrational modes of the lattice. Three characteristic Raman peaks are generally used to investigate the thickness, crystalline size, defect density, and doping level of graphene: the G-band ($\sim 1585 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), the D-band ($\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and the 2D-band ($\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The graphite mode (G-band) is characteristic of the in-plane C-C stretching in sp^2 -carbons. The associated quantised vibrational modes are the longitudinal optic (LO) phonon and the in-plane transverse optic (iTO) phonon. The peak positions for these two phonon modes are highly sensitive to strain, so although they overlap exactly for graphene, they become split for carbon nanotubes and strained graphene. The G-band position is also highly sensitive to doping (Fermi-level shifts). This is due to the strong electron-phonon coupling that arises from the inability of the electron cloud to keep up with the high-frequency in-plane atomic vibrations (non-adiabatic relaxation). This makes the G-band ideal for probing work function shifts in graphene as a result of chemical doping or field-effect modulation.

The 2D-band (also referred to as the G^2 -band) is the result of a double resonance process by which a phonon scatters the system between two electronic states. This is in contrast with more common non-resonant (no electronic transitions) and singly resonant (one photoexcited electronic transition) processes, and can occur with one or

two scattering phonons. In the first case referring to Figure D.2, an electron is photoexcited into the conduction band of the graphene and immediately transitions to another electronic conduction state by scattering a phonon, q . Since the DOS of graphene is continuous, there is always an available state above the Fermi level into which the electron can transition before relaxing back to the valence band by scattering a photon. In order to conserve momentum (excluding symmetry breaking disorder), a second phonon must backscatter the electron into a virtual state with the same wavevector as the initial photoexcitation. It turns out that the Raman shift for the DR process is highly dependent on excitation energy, causing the peak position to increase with increasing laser energy. The DR process provides a powerful method of probing the band structure of graphene. In this way, the 2D-band can be used to identify the number of layers as the electronic structure changes from a single Dirac cone for graphene, to several parabolic bands for bilayer and multilayer graphene. As the number of layers increases, the shape of the 2D-band transforms from a single Lorentzian to multiple overlapping peaks for multilayer graphene. The electronic band structure is also highly sensitive to changes in layer stacking, substrate and environmental effects.

Figure D.2 The double resonance process in graphene. (A) The defect mediated one-phonon, and (B) the momentum conserved two-phonon intravalley DR processes. (C) The dispersive nature of the DR process. The Raman peak associated with this process is dependent on the excitation energy

The Raman disorder modes (D and D'-bands) are the result of symmetry breaking in the two-dimensional graphene lattice. The sensitivity of phonon modes and electronic structure to the local lattice symmetry make Raman spectroscopy attractive for probing defect structures in sp^2 -carbons. The requirement for conservation of momentum in the electron-phonon scattering process can be mediated by elastic scattering with a defect. For this reason, the single-phonon D-peak is found at roughly half the frequency shift of the two-phonon 2D-peak.

APPENDIX E Reliability of Hall Effect Measurement

HMS-3000 provides simple Hall effect measurement for bulk and thin film samples. However, one should carefully consider several things before accurately extract the measured value out of the system. Hall effect measurement works on basis of ‘drift current’ within the sample under test. The presence of other carrier transport mechanisms (such as diffusion, thermionic, field emission, and tunnelling current) thus need to be eliminated or minimised. In simpler term, metal probe contacts need to form an ohmic contact with the sample under test without inducing any unnecessary energy barrier especially in case of semiconductor materials.

Figure E.1 shows the I-V characteristic of 4 point probes of HMS-3000 on a GO thin film. Probes materials are gold-coated copper, thus gold (work function around 5.1 eV) is the one in contact with the GO. Since it is already expected that majority carrier in GO would be a hole, so basically there will be no barrier for hole transport. The carrier transport mechanism is then dominated by hole drifting across the film (perhaps there is a low magnitude of the diffuse current component at gold-GO contact but can be neglected).

Figure E.1 I-V characteristic of a GO film with desired ohmic contacts

Once the ohmic contact between probes and sample are confirmed, now user can proceed to Hall effect measurement. Figure E.2 shows the main window of HMS-3000 system. The system is capable to extract out the sheet and bulk properties of the material. Bulk properties most of the time hold the utmost importance, however, user

needs to provide a pre-measured thickness of the sample for the system. The thickness input and bulk properties output are indicated by red boxes in Figure E.2.

After the measurement is conducted, the user needs to evaluate the reliability of the measurement by referring to blue box section as indicated in Figure E.2. The system conducts the measurement by repeating sweeping the current across the 4 probes and invert the polarity of the perpendicular magnetic field. Let each probe named as A, B, C, and D; so now we obtained the measured potential of AB, BC, AC, CD, DA, and BD. In the presence of magnetic field, we obtained MAC, -MAC, MBD, and -MBD. In the case of the sample does not violate van der Pauw formalism, the values in each boxes should not vary much for each repeated measurement except only inversion (positive/negative) of the value. If immediate measurement data is satisfying, so the result for sheet and bulk properties of the sample under test can be accurately interpreted.

Figure E.2 Main window of HMS-3000 system for Hall effect measurement

APPENDIX F Solar Simulator and 1-Sun

Figure F.1 shows the irradiation of AM0 and AM1.5G according to ASTM G173-03. The AM0 is the irradiance at extraterrestrial with an integrated power density of 136.6 mW/cm^2 . Upon reaching the terrestrial level, light is scattered by particles in the atmosphere depending on the value of AM. The AM1.5G is having integrated power density of 100 mW/cm^2 and it represents 1-sun.

Figure F.1 Solar irradiance according to ASTM G173-03

Newport LCS-100 uses ozone-free xenon lamp to simulate the solar irradiance. Figure F.2 and F.3 show the simulated irradiance of AM0 and AM1.5G, respectively by LCS-100 using AM filter.

Figure F.2 Spectral output of LCS-100 solar simulator with AM0 filter

Figure F.3 Spectral output of LCS-100 solar simulator with the AM1.5G filter

The lamp should be warmed up at least 10 minutes to be stable, and a detector should be placed in the intended working plane to monitor the output adjustment. Working distance is defined as the distance from the output port bottom surface to the target plane. Since the output beam is slightly divergent, adjusting the working distance has an inverse effect on the irradiance. The LCS-100 has been factory adjusted for best uniformity at a working distance of 8 inches, where it is certified. However, the uniformity is generally within Class B for working distance within the range of 6 to 10 inches. Table F.1 shows the relation between working distance and output power.

Table F.1 Output power from LCS-100 based on the distance of sample-source

Working distance from the output flange (inches)	Readings with AM0 filter (mW/cm^2)	Readings with AM1.5G filter (mW/cm^2)
6	247	161
7	184	119
8	151	100
9	126	82
10	105	69

As the lamp ages, the working distance will need to be reduced to maintain 1-sun output. This is accomplished by means of the mounting rod or target device height adjustment.